

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B414
 Date: 04 Nov 2008
 Take Off: 09:44:48
 Landing: 15:04:04
 Flight Time 5h 19m 16s

Campaign: VOCALS – 20 south task

Operating Area: S.E. Pacific Ocean off the coast of northern Chile

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Jackie Mullholland	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Phil Brown	Met Office	
6	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
7	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
9	SWS/SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	CCN	Guy Gratton	FAAM	
11	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
12	MARSS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
13	Mission Scientist 3	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
14	Wet neph / PSAP / Neph / filters	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
15	VACC	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
16	Manchester cloud / AMS / SP2	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
17	CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	
18				
19				

Flight Track:

B414 Track 04-NOV-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B414

Date: 4 November 2008

Project: VOCALS

Location: 20 South over Pacific Ocean off north Chile coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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091804		gin	0.08 kft	023	on
093852		ASP	0.08 kft	314	open
094448		T/O	0.05 kft	199	Arica
094448	095121	Profile 1	0.40 - 6.0 kft	201	start as t/o 6000ft
095121	100334	Run 1	6.0 kft	220	start as end P1
095222		nev	6.0 kft	221	zero
095340		JW	6.0 kft	227	zero
095512		heimann	6.0 kft	225	cal 09
100334	101028	Profile 2	6.0 - -.05 kft	227	50ft qnh1017
100637		!	3.0 kft	227	cloud top
100651		!	2.8 kft	225	at 3100ft
100725		!	2.2 kft	230	cloud base 2400
101028	101130	Profile 3	-.05 - 0.39 kft	229	50ft qnh1017 500ft
101130	102138	Run 2.1	0.39 - 0.44 kft	229	500ft
101242		JW	0.38 kft	225	zero
102042		!	0.39 kft	227	qnh 1018
102138	102236	Profile 4	0.44 - 1.4 kft	270	
102236	102719	Run 2.2	1.4 kft	268	
102257		!	1.4 kft	268	1500ft
102328		nev	1.4 kft	267	zero
102341		JW	1.4 kft	264	zero
102720	102850	Profile 5	1.4 - 2.9 kft	267	
102850	103416	Run 2.3	2.9 kft	272	
102941		r2.3	2.9 kft	266	3000ft cloud base 2700ft
103416	103620	Profile 6	2.9 - 4.8 kft	272	
103535		!	4.2 kft	269	tops 3900ft
103620	104650	Run 2.4	4.8 - 4.9 kft	269	
103654		r2.4	4.9 kft	268	5000ft
104650	105345	Profile 7	4.9 - -.08 kft	273	50 ft qnh1019
105346	105436	Profile 8	-.08 - 0.38 kft	273	50 ft qnh1019
105436	110439	Run 3.1	0.38 - 0.36 kft	269	
105513		r3.1	0.44 kft	268	500ft
110439	110752	Profile 9	0.36 - 3.6 kft	269	
110752	111811	Run 3.2	3.6 - 3.4 kft	265	
110830		!	3.5 kft	263	r3.2 reset to 3600ft
111812	111920	Profile 10	3.4 - 4.4 kft	273	
111920	113002	Run 3.3	4.4 - 4.5 kft	272	
111946		r3.3	4.4 kft	267	500ft above cloud
112404		heimann	4.5 kft	276	cal 06
113002	113559	Profile 11	4.5 - -.08 kft	274	50ft qnh 1019
113600	113644	Profile 12	-.10 - 0.33 kft	267	50ft qnh 1019
113644	114649	Run 4.1	0.33 kft	270	
113818		heimann	0.33 kft	267	cal 09
113830		r4.1	0.33 kft	266	500ft
113856		JW	0.34 kft	266	zero check
113910		nev	0.38 kft	267	zero check
114649	115119	Profile 13	0.33 - 4.0 kft	267	
115119	120126	Run 4.2	4.0 kft	271	
115212		p13	4.0 kft	269	pop up above to check cloud top
120127	120235	Profile 14	4.0 - 4.9 kft	262	
120236	121509	Run 4.3	4.9 kft	271	
121509	121604	Profile 15	4.9 - 5.4 kft	270	
121618	123034	Run 5.1	5.4 kft	274	
121916		r5.1	5.3 kft	091	C130 run start: 1 mile south of C130 track
123035	123157	Profile 16	5.4 - 4.2 kft	093	
123157	124146	Run 5.2	4.2 kft	087	
124146	124530	Profile 17	4.2 - 0.33 kft	096	
124531	125534	Run 5.3	0.33 - 0.38 kft	097	

124612		r5.3	0.34 kft	094 qnh 1020
125534	131626	Profile 18	1.1 - 23.0 kft	047
131626	142508	Run 6	23.0 - 22.9 kft	058
131924		Sonde 1	23.0 kft	082
132508		Heimann	23.0 kft	092 cal 06
132943		Sonde 2	23.0 kft	098
133950		Sonde 3	23.0 kft	091
135015		Sonde 4	23.0 kft	093
140040		Sonde 5	23.0 kft	096
141113		Sonde 6	23.0 kft	088
142121		Sonde 7	22.9 kft	090
142508	150403	Profile 19	22.9 - 0.07 kft	039 Arica
144309		p19	7.0 kft	054 interrupted fl070
144931		P19	6.9 kft	359 restarted
145221		P 19	5.0 kft	205 interrupt
145551		p19	4.9 kft	030 restart
150404		Land	0.07 kft	201 Arica
150631		ASP	0.07 kft	019 closed

B414 Track 04-NOV-08

FAAM Sortie, Flight B414 - VOCALS 20°S Cross-section #4
Tues 4th November 2008

T/O - 0645 local (0945 UTC) – to change to a later time only if C-130 T/O is delayed.
Landing ~1145 local (1445 UTC)

Mission Scientists: Paul Barrett, Phil Brown, Keith Bower

Operating Area: SE Pacific Ocean, off west coast of northern Chile, along lat line 20S

Waypoints: **ALPHA:** 72°W 20°S
BRAVO: 79°30'W 20°S
DART Buoy 74°46.804'W 19°35.583'S

Sortie Objectives: To sample aerosol and Sc cloud as a function of distance from the coast to the pristine background (at times operating simultaneously with the Dornier 228 which will be remote sensing from FL150 - along same latitude) and to inter-compare in-situ cloud, aerosol and chemistry instruments/measurements with the C-130.

Weather: High pressure system off shore capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud.

Detailed Flight schedule: PTO

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – as per instructions.

ARIES – as per instructions

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode: **AMS** and **SP2** to sample from it

Wet Neph – operated during all of 500ft runs

Drosondes – 1 per degree of longitude on high level return between BRAVO and ALPHA

AMS, SMPS, SP2 – to operate from Rosemount inlets during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; to operate on CVI during in-cloud runs.

Filters – to be exposed on below cloud runs at discretion of mission Scientist(s). Blank to be undertaken on high level return. The sample tube should be blown through before first filter cartridges deployed

FAAM Sortie, Flight B414 - VOCALS 20°S Cross-section #4

Detailed Flight schedule:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 6,000 ft amsl to check instrumentation
2. Continue towards ALPHA, beginning cycle below starting with immediate profile descent to 50ft.
3. Perform cycle consisting of a-i below
 - a. profile descent to 50ft amsl,
 - b. profile climb to 500ft amsl
 - c. carry out 10 min straight and level run (SLR) at 500ft amsl
 - d. * On first cycle only profile climb to 1500ft and carry out 3min SLR for CVI flow validation
 - e. climb to 500ft below cloudbase (CB),
 - f. carry out 10-min SLR at 500ft below CB,
 - g. climb to 500ft below cloud top (CT),
 - h. carry out 10-min SLR at 500ft below CT,
 - i. profile ascent to 1000ft above CT.
4. At point ALPHA turn onto westerly heading and continue profile cycle as described.
5. Repeat item 3 until arrival at point near to BRAVO. Continue on straight and level course and following communication with C-130 turn onto easterly heading to come into formation with C-130 to begin intercomparison legs [T=2h 25m]
6. Carry out 10min SLR at 500ft above CT, then descend to a point in-cloud at FL to be advised by the C-130.
7. Fly 10-minute straight and level in-cloud trailing the C-130 by 5 minutes.
8. Descend to 500 ft below cloud and fly 10 minute straight and level run.
9. Ascend to FL230 and turn to head west towards BRAVO until reaching a point along 20S from which to return to ALPHA (chosen so as to make full use of remaining fuel). After first contacting G1 and Do228 on guard freq 123.45MHz to liaise re: respective aircraft positions, begin to drop one sonde every 1 degree in longitude travelled towards ALPHA. NB no sondes to be dropped between point ALPHA and Arica on return.
10. Continue from point ALPHA to recover to Arica at FL230 as far as possible until approach into Arica and land [T=5h 00m]

Bae146 Mission Scientist Debrief

4 Nov 2008

Flight B414

20-Deg South Cross Section

Paul Barrett

Way Points Alpha: 20.0S 72.0W

 Bravo: 20.0S 79.5W

Take off 09:44 UTC

Land 15:04 UTC

Operating area: Southern Eastern Pacific ocean to the west of Arica, Chile

GOES-10 Thermal IR Image 1258UTC 4/11/08

Summary

A mission to characterise the stratocumulus along the 20S line, including sub cloud and above cloud legs. An intercomparison with the NCAR C-130 on three runs. Dropsondes dropped from 23kft every degree from 78 to 72 degrees west.

Weather Conditions

Stratocumulus was present across most of the operations area, except for a break in the cloud from just off the coast, and running a few miles out from the coast. The stratocumulus deck was not uniform across the area, and was very thin in places, and broken in places. A layer of cirrus clouds was present above, around 4/8 to 5/8 at the beginning of the sortie, rising to 8/8 in places on the return leg. In the early morning the cirrus layer was opaque in places, by the mid morning the layer was a cirro-stratus layer.

Points of Note

- Very light boundary layer winds. So very little turbulent transport, moisture flux.
- Cloud: LWC maximums generally approximately 0.5g/m³
- Drop concentrations fell away from the coast, 500 cc-1 near coast, to 350, then 200 near to 79W as given by FSSP (Manchester), CDP gave similar but with systematically lower concentrations, 250, 160, 135 cc-1. Mean droplet radius increase respectively.
- Some structure in the moisture profile in the boundary layer

- Very little drizzle was observed during the sortie
- The cloud was very thin, never more than about 1000ft. Cloud base did not vary smoothly as in previous 20S flights, but was much lower in places, and broken in others.-
- The particular case of the marine stratocumulus capped boundary layer topped by a cirrus layer as seen today may provide useful boundary conditions for a model study of the evolution of the boundary layer and the stratocumulus top.
- The boundary layer was well mixed *away from* the coast, towards 80 degrees. Closer to the coast the boundary layer showed signs of being decoupled, with small cumulus clouds forming below the stratocumulus. The cumulus did not seem to penetrate the tops of the stratocumulus

Mission Profile

Details

Profile climb from Arica to above the boundary layer, at 6kft.

Straight and level run (SLR) at 6kft – radiation measurements of the cirrus above. The Sc was not present below at the start of the run.

The aircraft turned at point alpha (72W 20S) and began to head west along 20S

Following this a series of runs was commenced.

- A profile to the surface (50ft) and back up to 500ft, to characterise the boundary layer.
- SLR at 500ft, to sample the sub cloud region.
- SLR in cloud. Cloud top and base estimates were taken from the previous profile.
- SLR above cloud with radiation instruments (SWS, ARIES) assessing the impact of the Ci on cloud top radiative balance
- Climbs between SLRs were all profile climbs (1000ft/min)

A total of three sets took places, until the most westerly point was reached.

The aircraft turned to head east, and climb to follow the track of the C-130 running 5 minutes ahead. Intercomparison runs were performed following the C-130 above cloud at ----ft, 4500ft in cloud and 500ft AMSL.

The BAe146 then climbed to 23kft heading west to reach 78 degrees west. The return along 20S saw a sonde dropped every degree on the degree until 72W. The NCAS Dornier228 DCALM was in the air close to the sonde at 76 degrees, and the G1 and the Twin Otter were also in the air along the same track during this sortie.

A profile descent was performed into Arica on recovery.

Instruments Issues

2DS – not much data recorded – redundancy exists in other instruments

PCASP – u/s – dirty optics, leak, concentrations far too high – can use CVI-PCASP out of cloud

Lower SHIMS – Low signal

Sondes – all data recorded, including GPS winds

CCN Rack – lost data from the first 30 minutes, software control issues(?), 'B' column is working 'A' column is u/s, No data from final climb after ~12kft, and no data on 23kft leg

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B/A/A... Date 4/11/20 Name P. BARRETT Page ...1... of ...7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
09:44	P1				TAXI - overcast, 8/8 sea haze cloud base @ 2.2 kft cloud top @ 3? some breaks
09:58					line clearance of coastal Sc
09:59	R1	6.0 kft			Sc above horizon edge of Sc visible on horizon small wisps of cloud in clear sbt edge very well defined inversion at 3.0 kft well mixed B-L some structure (moisture) above horizon
10:04					above Sc - thin, some clear patches visible to West constant depth below inversion P1
10:11	P2				breaks to - altitudes → Pressure setting cloud top 3.1 kft (1015) cloud base ~ 2.6 kft Cu below non-uniform cloud base some drizzle on wind screen
10:14	R2	500ft			(-130 22.55 80W POC - reported @ 17:15 4500ft in clouds

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 414 Date 4/11/08 Name P. BARRITT Page 2 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	R21 (to 10:15)				All non-uniform cloud base. slight drizzle. P=1018 clear above in places
10:28					POINT X
	P4				
	R22				CUI zero Some cells are much lower than general base.
	P5				Cloud base ~2500 (lowest)
	R23				entered ~2700 LWC ~0.05 g/m ³ out of cloud cloud base 1/4 above cloud (20)
10:40:20	R24	S.0			S _c = 8/8 C _i = 4/8 all stratus broken Some Ac -6/8 above as well? Dust deposits on wind screen
				CD ²	ISS-173 $\phi = 13 \rightarrow 10 \mu\text{m}$ ASSP 350 $\rho = 14 \rightarrow 10 \mu\text{m}$ Direct ~5 h ⁻¹ 100 μm
					Radiation Measurements
104650	P7	S.0-0.5			Obs. C _{top} = 4/8 C _{base} = 2/8 (1/8) LWC ~0.3 max = 0.4 Bl dewpoint structure at 960hPa dewpoint looks well mixed
	P8	0.5-500			S 8/8

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...414... Date 4/1/08... Name P. BARRETT... Page 3 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
108436	3.1	500			still thin cloud, some small breaks to sky
					21°23'580W 4.4
					Sat images - 1hr broken to 77 SW
110434					light winds - off rd from C130 break
	3.2	3800			cloud base ~ 3.2 kft
		3600			slight adjustment
					1
					so 75.09 W
					CCN - increase 350-500
					still cloud tops, some surface veg
					COP 250 $\rho = 11 \mu m$
					FSSP 500 $\rho = 11 \mu m$
11:14.20	R3.3	4600			Thin cloud below, broken Sc in dec
					Ci above, all the way to horizon
					CCN - lower so 200-300
					wind increase above inversion.
					hole in Sc below
					(boundary ahead, change in cloud height)
	PA				Cloud Top = 4.1 (1019)
					C130 ~ 3.7 (1019)
	PL				
11:36.44	RA.1	5000			below broken Sc light wind
					some moisture in structure to cloud

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 44 Date Name PBARZEN Page 4 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations
					(cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
113649	P13	500 - 4400			Profile through cloud cloud base = 34 scattered Main base = 3650 Cloud top = 4.4 CPC logged to 250
11.31.14	R4.2	4.1kft			23 mins to RV 12.15 1200ft 6.000ft 30.17 9/4 nearly in cloud top ASAP 350 φ 14 COP 160 φ 15 drizzle 3 l ⁻¹ 100µm Cu 15 cc ⁻¹ water not raining much
	D14				cloud top at 4.4
12:02:36	R4.3				above cloud Ci patchy above Sc - solid below hole above. C130 - CTop @ 4.5kft
12.14	S.1			intocamp	above cloud @ 5.5kft We are off at 1hr to the south RIS start of C-130 run M30A - descending Longitude = 078°47.4' 4300ft 3000ft on border Sc ahead

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 444 Date Name P. BARRETT Page 5 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	P16				cloud top (1019 3000) = A. 6kft
	R52				Pass 200 P = 18µm
					CDDP 125 → 150 P = 19µm
					Drizzle 10 L ⁻¹
					CAS = similar size 15µm
					conc = 400 cc ⁻¹
					hitting cloud top
					0.1 LWC
					10-20 on PLASP } CVD
					60 on CPC }
					LWC - gm ~ 0.3
					N _v 0.21, 0.26
					75°06' end of run
					gone time - hitting cloud top
12:40					G1 20 78
12:41	P17				CBox 3700
					sunlight down to sea surface
					well mixed, no visible structure to top
12:45.4	S3				77°14' - end of C1 to intercept
					CW PLASP ~ 150 cc ⁻¹
					All aircraft in the air
					G1, DCALM, C-130, TUNO, etc.
12:53.24	P18				Cloud top ~ 4.2 kft

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...414... Date 4/11/08... Name P. BARRETT Page 6 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	P16				- dry aloft
					Pic 306 - taken 3000/6000 ft
					- Boundary - lift?
					filled in - not re-opened??
13:16	Q6	23000			Sonde leg, all aircraft in air
13:24					SONDE 1
					- Ci above, 3/8
					ahead Ci, Ci stratus, Altostratus
					- Pic 310 Ci solid ahead
13:29:43					Sonde 2
					Pic 311 - open structure.
					radiometer 1 min zenith before after sun
					radir rest of run
					734 330
					2 layers above? - high Ci
					and the Ac? - could be thinner
					parts of the same layer.
					is it?
13:45 13:45?					Pic 245, 316
14:00:10					Sonde 5 - 74° W less Ci above Pic 317
					Cu forming in gaps between Sc Pic 318
14:11:13					Sonde 6 - 73° W

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. A114 Date 4/1/08 Name PBARRETT Page 7 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					} large rift in Sc to SE in } towards coast - nothing in there (Cu)
				PIC 314	
					} Rift ahead, some Cu built up } at this longitude
				Sign rift on the	
14.16				PIC 320 - Cu in rift, on 20S	
14.18				PIC 322 - rift edge, Ci above.	
				Sonde 7, dropped on rift	
14.21				boundary	
	P19			descent back into arica.	
				moist layer on descent	
		10000ft		Passing edge of Sc NW	
				Haze and low cloud on Andes.	
				convection in a line over distant	} mountains.
				terrace, two layers @ 200	
				Ci above airfield	
				↳ No Pirouette as requested	

Mission Scientist's Log

Miss. Sci.
2

Flight No B. 414 Date 4/11/08 Name Phil Brown Page 1 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
0944		-			t/o ARI.
		¹⁰¹³ 2700			cloud top. 5/8 Ci above
0951		6000			clear area starts about here - quite extensive ahead.
0957.17		"	277		over Sc edge again. Start PD.
100322		" ↓			" "
—		²⁰⁰⁰ 3100	1017		3000 cloud tops.
—					1/8 scudgy Cu below Sc
10028					end PD
1017	2.1	500			Still seems to be Cu below Sc ahead.
—					
102236	2.2	1500			R2.2 start for Cu eval.
102720					end.
102801		2500 2100			Cu patch here.
		2700			a cloud.
102850	2.3	3000	W	72.5W	2.3 start 2DC 5-10L-1
103416		"			end 2.3 early, climb up.
103620	2.4	5000		73.W	2.4 streaks of dirt on screen from in clouds.
1044					CCN now OK.
104650		"		73.42'W	2.4 end
		^{6.8} 4100			cloud top
105345		50'		74.2W	end PD seems more well-mixed.
105436	3.1	500			start 3.1 176/5ms ⁻¹

Mission Scientist's Log

Miss. Sci
2

Flight No B. 214 Date 4/11/08 Name Page 2 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
110639	3.1	500			end. e TQ to 3800.
					CCN 350-500 area in counts.
110830	3.2	3600		75.60W	cloud top at 3800
/					well mixed BL during climb
/					CDP 250 1µm MF 500
1113					CVI low hwc - adjust cut.
/					2DC v. low drizzle.
1116					probably nearer base than top at this end of run.
111812	3.2				end 4100 top
111920	3.3	11600		75 48.6W	start 3.3 CCN 200-300
					305/8 ms ⁻¹
1126					Heiman in cal as we cross broken cloud, but
/					probably seeing flow to etc.
					end 3.3
					4000 tops.
					3500 base.
/					route is cooler & drier than before
113559		50ft			end-P11
113644	4.1	500		76.9 W	start 4.1 but quite well-mixed. extra moisture
/					at 500ft & below?
					177/7 ms ⁻¹
114449	4.1	//			end 4.1
		3650			base.
		4400			tops.

Mission Scientist's Log

Miss. Sci
2

Flight No B...414 Date 4/11/08 Name Page 3 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
115719	4-2	4100			Start 4-2.
					C130 QNH 30.17
					MF 350 14 CDP 160 15
/					5 L ⁻¹ 100µm 2DC.
/					CDP clean spectra.
					Do 228 at to 76w 100-150
120127	4-2	"			end 4-2 4400 tops.
120236	4-3	5000			start - still Ci above & drifting 4 mi N for separ.
121618		5500 ^{30.17}	W		Run 5.1 250/3 ms ⁻¹
1217					turning back E to follow C130
121856		"			in trail 1 mi S, just thro aerosol spike, exhaust plume.
					GPS alt 1700-1720 m
123035					end 5.1 & start descent
/					4600 ft tops 1328 m GAL for a cloud.
123157		4300			Start 5.2 +/- 10 m fluctuation.
					5-10 L ⁻¹ 2DC 200µm
/					MF 200 18µm CDP 125-150 Apr
					CAS 400 clean spectra
/					CVI 0.1 gm ⁻³ JW ~ 0.3
/					0.3-0.45 JW
124146			E	FBW	end 5.2 3700 base.
124531		500			start 5.3. well mixed in descent.
					117 6 ms ⁻¹
/					note large error in distance to ACRS offset

Mission Scientist's Log

MS 2

Flight No B. 414 Date 4/11/08 Name Page 4 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	5.3	500			150 cu ³ cu, PCASP
125534		"			end 5.3 e Profile 18 to Fl 230
					4200 tops.
131626	6	Fl 230	060	78 12.0w initially	end P18, run 6
131924		"	090	78 W	Sonde 1
1323				77.300w	broken cloud below.
/					v. dry above inversion in P18,
/					GE wandering down slowly to -50
					270/17ms ⁻¹
132943				77 W	Sonde 2 good GPS.
133950				76W	Sonde 3
135015				75 W	sonde 4
140040				74W	sonde 5 270/12
1411		"			broken cloud to N, variable cloud thickness.
141113				73W	Sonde 6
142124				72W	Sonde 7
142508	6	"	040		End 6, start P19
1431					solid cloud in near coast region again.
1434					moist layer started at 550hPa L seen also in CAS.
143920		9100			clear below again, aerosol layer just below.
144315		5000			hold P19. Shows in Nepht.

1504

land
5h 19.

Mission Scientist's Log (MSi3)

(+ MAN CLOUD RACK OF 2)

Flight No **B.414**.....

Date **04/11/08** (K.N. BOWEN).....

Page **1** of **6**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
6:45:07	KWB ϕ mi				T/D
					lit d SO ₂ 8 μ g/h ³ AMS ✓
09:44:48	P1 from TB				CAS sensing alt at static sharp drop in both AMS/ATMS out of BL
09:49:40					Dehaze edge to Sc ~ 4000ft. in CAS in BL
09:51:21	P1 ^{out} /R1	6000	224	18°36'/70°50'	16.04°/-4.21°C 813mb 5m/s/161° (5.9kft)
					Broken below / Ci above
09:57:22	R1	6000			at edge of next batch Sc (Cont)
10:03:33	R1 ^{out} /P2	5.9kft	227	19°12'/71°6'	15.08°/-1.74°C 812mb 2m/s/179°
10:06:40	P2	2.9kft	226	18°52'/71°58'	CT = ~ 3000ft 908mb 18.52/4.86 3m/s/111
10:07:15	P2	2.3kft	231	19°24'/71°18'	CB = ~ 2400ft 929mb 11.94/12.41 5m/s/78
10:10:25	P2/P3 E	0 kft	228	19°30'/71°50'	1014mb 18.02/15.54°C 7m/s/165°
10:11:31	P3 ^{out} /R2	0.3kft	229	19°30'/71°30'	C130 @ 22.55 '80W in PDC still reporting RV @ 12:15 UTC ⇒ include leg @ 4500ft.
10:20:16	R2.1				1018 press setting
10:21:40	R2.1/P4	0.4kft	269	19°54'/72°0'	Tuned at oc (cont R2.1 start P4
10:23:36	P4 ^{out} /R2.2	1.3kft	268	19°54'/72°0'	AMS → CV1 13.522/11.41° 965mb 3/197° Binned SMOSS Spectra Great AMS signal on CV5 unit.
10					
10:27:59	R2.2/PS	1.3kft	267	20°0'/72°24'	end R2.2 / start PS 964mb 13.25/10.82° 5m/s/238
10:28:48	PS/R2.3	2.8kft	272	20°/72°30'	end PS start R2.3 in cloud 913mb 8.82/9.76°C 0 m/s

0.1 g/h³ JW, Newzean, CAS 0.15 g/h³ ϕ = 13um
CAS LWC = 0.2 g/m³

Mission Scientist's Log (MSci3)

Flight No B.414 Date 04/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 2 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
10:32:52	R2.3	29kft	267	20°/72°42'	911mb 8.58/9.17°C 2m/s/112
10:35					2DS aircraft - rechecked - new marks ✓
10:36:21	P4ev/R2.4	4.8kft	269	20°/73°	846mb 19.01°C/10.46°C 7m/s/307°
				Captain	picked up marks on windscreens on cloud from clouds - streaks of dust on windscreens
					SWS - 1 minute window for each ch
					Will do 500ft leg after P dump.
					check Cu bases through Sc - 1500ft
					min probable wind be
					Core Cloud CDP - conc (150 - 175) φ (13 → 10)
					FBSP - conc (300-350) φ (4-10)
					drag ~ 5-2 / h 100um (not much)
					(will stay on CM until in Ae - rather than track mark inlet)
10:46:28	R2.4/PS	49kft	273	20°/73°42'	846mb 19.52/-1.02 8m/s/292°
					Changed #
10:48:07	PS	3800	269	20°/73°42'	CT - 4100 on 1018mb sensor
10:49:30	PS	2600	271	20°/73°48'	CB on 2900 916mb 8.5/9.0°C 3m/s/174°
10:53:41	PS/p6	0kft	273	20°/74°08'	Gang to 500ft - CAS scan Dump (1018mb)
10:54:36	P6ev/R3.1	0.3kft	269	20°/74°12'	999mb 15.16/9.08° 5m/s/177°
10:57:30					Disc'n VACC CAS scan 2nd marker
					3mg/m ³ total Core orb 3.5-4/cm ³

low wind speed - little sea roll at all

Mission Scientist's Log (MSi3)

Flight No B.....⁴⁹¹⁴ Date 04/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 3 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					rising in channel 1 - total ~300 cm ² but these ones 10x higher than should be, -2DS OK.
					- good LWC on COPS - clear is <u>0</u>
					C130 @ 215 80W
500ft 11.04.53	R3.1e / P1	0.4kft	269	20°/74°48'	907mb 15.04/9.52°C 4m/s/173° Switch AMS to CFI in prep for inched run
					Got flow - no particle
					CPC 9
11.07.52	R3.2 / R3.2	3.6kft	265	20°/75°W	887mb 5.79/7.14°C 4m/s/183°
11.08.30	R3.2 skd	3600	266	20°/75°6'	Start dual run - in CT's
					COP 250 $\bar{\phi}$ 11 _{mn}
					PCASP 800 ϕ 11-12
					ONE LWC n=0 3.2-4 particle/cm ³ such small drops maybe ϕ / flow still
11.16.08	R3.2	3.4kft	273	20°/75°42'	893mb 5.52/7.01 5m/s/175
11.18.49	R3.2end / P10	3900	270	20°/75°42'	877mb 5.35/5.91°C 3m/s/175
11.19.21	P10 / R3.3	4400	271	20°/75°48'	500 ft above CT. clear air - AMS → Rose (FL045)
					CPC ~ 200-300 cm ²
					PCASP ~ (missed it)
					PCASP track 15-20 "325/20kts wind"

Mission Scientist's Log (MSi 3)

Flight No B. 414 Date 04/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 4 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	R33				CAS < 0.1 cm ³
11.29.58	R33/P11	4.4kft	274	20°/76°24'	859mb 16°56'/-27.35°C 7m/s/132°
11.30.43	P11	4000	275	20°/76°30'	CT (4.1kft MSi)
11.31.25	P11	3400	270	20°/76°30'	CB (3.7kft MSi)
					2.5µg m ⁻³ Si ₂
50ft 11.35.57	P11ex/P12	0.0kft	267	20°/76°46'	1016mb 16.2/8.57°C 5m/s/165°
500ft 11.36.41	P12ex/R4.1	0.3kft	270	20°/76°54'	1007mb 15.05/8.2°C 5m/s/165° ferred LW probe on CAS
					CIP W/W
					CAS ~ 2.5 cm ⁻³
					Reforming CT ~ 3800ft
11.35.2				C130	21.34S 80W ab 4500ft
500ft 11.46.44	R4.1ex/P13	0.3kft	267	20°/77°30'	1000mb 15.07/8.98° 7m/s/127°
11.48ish					AMS → CVI ml/d
11.49.52	P13	3.5kft	267	20°S/77°42'	CD 890mb 6.01°/6.63° 7m/s/174°
11.50.26	P13	4.2kft	267	20°S/77°48'	CT 868mb 4.53°/6.65° 6m/s/163°
11.50.37	P13/ex	4.4kft	268	20°S/77°48'	not called as probe down into cloud Run
11.51.17	desc/R4.2	3.9kft	270	20°S/77°46'	875mb 5.06°/10.06° 6m/s/155mb SO ₂ high on AMS Cr50 Brake 3 CIP v CAS ✓ Cin Cloud FSSP ~ 350 φ 14µm COP ~ 160 φ 15µm few drizzle v 3-4/d CAS 350-400 φ 14-15µm CIT KASO 15µm/ce

5500 407 nm
C130

Mission Scientists Log (MSci 3)

Flight NO B 414 Date 09/11/08 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 5 of 6

TIME (GMT)	Run/Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS POSITION	REMARKS/OBSERVATIONS
11.57 ish	R4.2				2DS cracked - rest - new marks - OK.
12.01.36	R4.2/P14	4100	262	20°/75°31'	CT still at 4400ft 871mb 4.79/1278
12.02.37	P14/R4.3	4500	271	20°/75°36'	will drift off 20S for a/c Vcompensation
					3m/s/257
					130 α Rance.
	R4.3/P5				
12.15.37	P5and/R5.1	5200	272	19°54'/71°24'	833mb 15.89/-22.51°C 4m/s/185°
12.16.42	R5.1	5300	271	19°54'/71°30'	turning 831mb 15.82/-29.82 4mb/172°
12.19 ish					Crossed Central C130 - CRC/VACC.
12.18.56	R5.1	5300	90°	20°/79°30'	turn completed 830mb 15.33/-32.01°C 4/125°
12.30.30	R5.1/P16	5300	93°	20°/78°46'	R:24 C130 ↓ (gaining down)
12.31.54	P16	4400	89°	20°/78°42'	860mb 6.46/-22.49° 7/125° [CT]
12.31.56	P16/R5.2	4100	87°	20°/78°42'	(CT = 4600 cabin)
					CRS seems higher ones
					Core Anal FSSP 200 φ=18μ
					CDP +125-150 φ~19μ
					W/E dust 200
					CAS 400 = falling at 5μ
					CVI 0.1g/m ³ W-20 PctOSP 600CR
					CRPS LWC 0.45 ish
1243nh					Switched AMS → Rose
12.41.51	R5.2/P17	4100	96°	20°/76°	872mb 5.02/7.39° 6m/s/135°
12.45.31	P17/R5.3	500ft			
12.55.32	R5.3/R6	500ft	94°	20°/77°15'	end vic end R5.3 890mb 15.07/9.05°
12.57.					changes AMS to MS only for high level
13.16.26	P17and/R6	FL230	96°	20°/75°12'	hours just started to see "2DS data"

prohibit and no cloud - did so by at bottom - had to had cloud - must
of
- above cloud
prof down

Cyde - out to W point
land - nr C150

repeat 3 Hc with C130 Smith behind

↑ PL230 → 76°W - damped sails → 72°

Prohibit down to Brin.

Se thin broken - Down Gues to as → W down size ↑

ci all way across

Int

VACE ✓
CMI - ones with 1

Falkus ✓
AMS ✓
2 JS → COPS ✓
lost some data

Core Chem man variable in O₃
CO

JW ✓
New ✓

Cloud Phys - had in PCOSM - analyzing optics - needs a chem
- convergence obs. - for need flight
- Cloud Inst O₂

SWS - Schemms -

MORE job

DAVES ✓

SONDES 7/7

CEN - had to be 1st 1/2 hour
restarted whole run

↳ only Beckman working
↳ shut down during desc

↳ sv N° CPC PL100

90° to permit H₂

SMRS ✓

http://192.168.101.71 - Plot - Mozilla Firefox

Flight B414 09:51:20
Heading 224 deg Speed 241 knots Height 5.9kft Press 813mb
Lat 18°36.0'S Long 70°30.0'W Wind 5 ms-1/ 161 deg
Temp 16.04C Dewpoint -4.12C

Track Plot Plot From: 09:21:20 To: now last 30 mins

Save plot parameters as Track Plot

Long 663.GIN LONGITUDE (deg (+ve E))

658.TECO NO2 (ppb)
659.TECO NOx (ppb)
660.NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER (g m-3)
661.NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER (g m-3)
662.GIN LATITUDE (deg (+ve N))

Lat 662.GIN LATITUDE (deg (+ve N)) Red Line Del

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

P1 end R1 start 6000ft

http://192.168.101.71 - Plot - Mozilla Firefox

Flight B414 10:03:33
 Heading 227 deg Speed 242 knots Height 5.9kft Press 812mb
 Lat 19°12.0'S Long 71°6.0'W Wind 2 ms-1/ 179 deg
 Temp 15.08C Dewpoint -1.74C

neph alt Plot From: 09:33:32 To: now last 30 mins

Save plot parameters as neph alt

Y 579.PRESSURE HEIGHT (Kft)

579.PRESSURE HEIGHT (Kft)
 580.SOLAR ALBEDO (-)
 581.NEAR INFRA-RED ALBEDO (-)
 582.VISIBLE ALBEDO (-)
 583.LOWER VISIBLE FLUX (W m-2)

X1 591.DEW POINT (TOTAL WATER) (deg C) Blue Cross Del

X2
 X3
 X4

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

R1 end P2 start

CT approx 3000ft

CB approx 2400ft

Flight B414 10:09:41
Heading 226 deg Speed 219 knots Height 0.3kft Press 1000mb
Lat 19°30.0'S Long 71°24.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 154 deg
Temp 16.99C Dewpoint 15.37C
From 09:19:01 to now

Current values
+---+ STATIC PRESSURE 1000.72 mb
+---+ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 17 deg C
+---+ DEW POINT 15.38 deg C

End P2 start P3 at 50ft

End P3 start R2.1 at 500ft

Display Range

00 d 10:12:40

Occ

v2.5.1

Hotwire_LWC Data

LWC - DAT Calc (g/m³)

LWC - DAT Obs (g/m³)

P Total (W)

DAT Calculated (W) DAT Calculated (g/m³)

DAT Observed (W) DAT Observed (g/m³)

LWC Hotwire (V) LWC raw (g/m³)

LWC Slave (V) Air Density (kg/m³)

Pressure (mBar) Airspeed (m/s)

Ambient Temp(C) Boiling Point (K)

1st Hotwire_LWC g/m³

DMT Particle Analysis and Display System

Program Configure

Display Range
00 d 10:12:53 Occ

Enable Enabled

COM Port v2.5.3

#Conc (#/cm ³)	Sum of Particles	LWC Hotwire (V)
<input type="text" value="8.22"/>	<input type="text" value="3698"/>	<input type="text" value="1.08"/>
CAS LWC (g/m ³)	Forward Overflow	LWC Slave Mon (V)
<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0.32"/>
CAS MVD (um)	Backward Overflow	Laser Curr Mon (mA)
<input type="text" value="2.11"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="87.5"/>
CAS ED(um)	Ambient Temp (C)	Laser Pwr Mon (V)
<input type="text" value="1.59"/>	<input type="text" value="NaN"/>	<input type="text" value="43.1"/>
Dynamic Pressure	Static Pressure	Airspeed (m/s)
<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="93.9"/>

DMT Particle Analysis and Display System

Program Configure

Sampling Recording Read a File

Display Range

00 d 10:13:07

0cc

All

(0) CIP Grayscale (1) CAS (2) Hotwire_LWC (3) SPP_200 Setup

CIP GS Data CIP GS Housekeeping CIP GS Cal **Enabled**

COM Port 3 **No Fault** v2.6.5

CIP GS # Conc/LWC CIP GS Realtime Images CIP GS Selectable Charts Full Hist. Diode Voltages

Numb Conc (cts/cm ³)	Oversize Reject Count	
0	0	
LWC (g/cm ³)	DOF Reject Count	
0	0	
MWD (um)	End Reject Count	
0	0	
ED (um)	Particle Counter	
0	0	
Diode 1 V	Diode 32 V	Diode 64 V
2.4	2.7	2.55

CIP GS LWC

CIP Grayscale Particle Counter

CIP GS # Conc

New plot, same times

Flight B414 10:19:07
Heading 225 deg Speed 217 knots Height 0.3kft Press 998mb
Lat 19°54.0'S Long 71°54.0'W Wind 5 ms-1/ 154 deg
Temp 16.34C Dewpoint 13.59C
From 09:48:50 to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	37146	secs	☒ All	☒ scr
—	JAW LIQUID WATER CONTENT	-0	g m-3	☐	
—	NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	0	g m-3	☐	

Turned at alpha end R2.1 startP4

End P4 start R2.2 at 1500ft

End R2.2 start P5

End P5 start R2.3

Program Configure

Display Range

00 d 10:30:25

Occ

All

Enable Enabled

COM Port

v2.5.3

4

CAS # Conc

CAS Data

#Conc (#/cm ³)	Sum of Particles	LWC Hotwire (V)
398.25	43955	1.25
CAS LWC (g/m ³)	Forward Overflow	LWC Slave Mon (V)
0.15	0	0.32
CAS MVD (um)	Backward Overflow	Laser Curr Mon (mA)
11.32	0	87.5
CAS ED(um)	Ambient Temp (C)	Laser Pwr Mon (V)
10.63	NaN	43
Dynamic Pressure	Static Pressure	Airspeed (m/s)
0	0	96.4

CAS Volume Conc

Display Range

00 d 10:30:52

0cc

Enable

Save Config

Get DAT Observed

Dry Air Term (g/m³)

v2.5.1

Dry Air Term (W)

Hotwire_LWC Data

LWC - DAT Calc (g/m³)

LWC - DAT Obs (g/m³)

P Total (W)

DAT Calculated (W)

DAT Calculated (g/m³)

DAT Observed (W)

DAT Observed (g/m³)

LWC Hotwire (V)

LWC raw (g/m³)

LWC Slave (V)

Air Density (kg/m³)

Pressure (mBar)

Airspeed (m/s)

Ambient Temp(C)

Boiling Point (K)

1st Hotwire_LWC g/m³

LWC - DAT Calc (g/m³)

LWC - DAT Obs (g/m³)

Sampling Recording Read a File

Display Range 00 d 10:31:07 All

(0) CIP Grayscale (1) CAS (2) Hotwire_LWC (3) SPP_200 Setup

CIP GS Data CIP GS Housekeeping CIP GS Cal Enable Enabled COM Port 3 No Fault v2.6.5

CIP GS # Conc/LWC CIP GS Realtime Images CIP GS Selectable Charts Full Hist. Diode Voltages

Numb Conc (cts/cm ³)	2.67	Oversize Reject Count	0		
LWC (g/cm ³)	0.01	DOF Reject Count	0		
MWD (um)	8.77	End Reject Count	0		
ED (um)	23.16	Particle Counter	85		
Diode 1 V	2.33	Diode 32 V	2.62	Diode 64 V	2.7

Main Display

H > V lbHVDiff V > H

Stereo Pairs: 0

Settings

V-time

Pro Att Pro

Set True Air Speed

100

Send New True Air Speed

Send Command Packet

	Heater Zone	Heater Threshold	Laser Drive	V AM
Vert. Transmit Arm Temp.	☒	5	V 3200	
Vert. Receive Arm Temp.	☒	5		
Vert. Laser Temp.	☒	20		
			Build V Mask ☒	
				Vertical
				MaxSlice 1000
				Rej. % 1
				MinSlice 10
				Spare (hex)
				SPARE0 FFFF
				SPARE FFFF
				SPARE0 FFFF
				SPARE 0200
				SPARE0 0078
				SPARE 0
				SPARE0 0
				SPARE 0

Click To Send Command Packet

Housekeeping Display Processed Data

Misc

Vertical particles detected: 265.0 TAS: 100

Can internal pressure: 12.40 TAS(FIXED):

Vertical masked bits: 0 Timing Word:

Temperatures

Vert. Transmit Arm Temp.: 12.1

Vert. Receive Arm Temp.: 11.3

Rear Optics Bridge Temp.: 24.4

DSP Board Temp.: 27.7

Forward Vessel Temp.: 21.4

Vert. Laser Temp.: 28.5

Front Plate Temp.: 14.4

Power Supply Temp.: 29.8

Supply Voltage

+5V: 5.01

-5V: -4.99

Raw power

+7V: 6.96

-7V: -7.15

Laser Drive

V: 3200

Element Voltages

	Vertical
0	2.8857
21	3.1982
42	3.1543
64	2.7124
85	1.9873
106	2.0801
127	2.9224

Compression

Blocks: 3

Vertical automask iterations: 0

V overload periods: 0

Compression configuration: Both

Spare 2: 38

Spare 3: 10003

Spare 4: 33435

SBC Temp1: Temp2: Pressure:

Set Probe Mask

Vertical

Current Mask: 1 - FFFF

New Mask: Modify

Set New Mask

FFFF

Enter new hex value for probe word # 0

Save Exit

Force All 1's

Bytes Received	Particles	Blocks	Mask	HK
52810926	2459158	12887	1	3062

R2.3 “in-cloud” but now out of cloud CB lifted

End P4 start run 2.4

End R2.4 start P5 down to 500ft

CT about 4100ft on 1018 mb

P5 CB 2900 on 1018

Sampling Recording Read a File

Display Range 00 d 10:53:25 All Occ

(0) CIP Grayscale (1) CAS (2) Hotwire_LWC (3) SPP_200 Setup

Enable Enabled

COM Port 4 v2.5.3 No Fault

CAS Data CAS Housekeeping

#Conc (#/cm ³)	Sum of Particles	LWC Hotwire (V)
4.05	1507	1.07
CAS LWC (g/m ³)	Forward Overflow	LWC Slave Mon (V)
0	0	0.3
CAS MVD (um)	Backward Overflow	Laser Curr Mon (mA)
2.1	0	87.7
CAS ED(um)	Ambient Temp (C)	Laser Pwr Mon (V)
1.6	NaN	43
Dynamic Pressure	Static Pressure	Airspeed (m/s)
0	0	93.9

Standard Charts Selectable Charts Forward/Backscatter

Forward Scattering Backward Scattering

End P5 at 50ft start P6 to 500ft

end P6 start R3.1 at 500ft

Display Range

00 d 10:57:41

OCC

All

Enable Enabled

COM Port v2.5.3

4

CAS Data CAS Housekeeping

Standard Charts Selectable Charts Forward/Backscatter

#Conc (#/cm ³)	Sum of Particles	LWC Hotwire (V)
5.07	1638	1.12
CAS LWC (g/m ³)	Forward Overflow	LWC Slave Mon (V)
0	0	0.32
CAS MVD (um)	Backward Overflow	Laser Curr Mon (mA)
3.27	0	87.5
CAS ED(um)	Ambient Temp (C)	Laser Pwr Mon (V)
2.28	NaN	43
Dynamic Pressure	Static Pressure	Airspeed (m/s)
0	0	93.8

Forward Scattering Backward Scattering

Zeroed but slave V is 0.0 still

P7 end R3.2 start includ run

End R3.1 at 500ft start P7

R3.2 incloud started 11:08:30 still in CTs

DMT Particle Analysis and Display System

Program *Configure*

Sampling

Recording

Read a File

Display Range

00 d 11:10:38

OCC

All

(0) CIP Grayscale

(1) CAS

(2) Hotwire_LWC

(3) SPP_200

Setup

Enable

Enabled

COM Port

v2.5.3

4

No Fault

CAS Data

CAS Housekeeping

#Conc (#/cm³)

518.56

Sum of Particles

47480

LWC Hotwire (V)

1.21

CAS LWC (g/m³)

0.06

Forward Overflow

0

LWC Slave Mon (V)

0.32

CAS MVD (um)

7.53

Backward Overflow

0

Laser Curr Mon (mA)

87.5

CAS ED(um)

7.53

Ambient Temp (C)

NaN

Laser Pwr Mon (V)

43

Dynamic Pressure

0

Static Pressure

0

Airspeed (m/s)

96.4

Standard Charts

Selectable Charts

Forward/Backscatter

CAS # Conc

Forward Scattering

Backward Scattering

CAS Volume Conc

New plot, same times

Flight B414 11:13:30

Heading 264 deg Speed 219 knots Height 3.5kft Press 891mb

Lat 20°0.0'S Long 75°24.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 162 deg

Temp 5.29C Dewpoint 6.88C

From start to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	40410	secs	☐ All	☒ scr
—	JAW LIQUID WATER CONTENT	0.08	g m-3	☐	
—	NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	0.07	g m-3	☐	

Sampling Recording Read a File

Display Range
All

00 d 11:14:54

OCC

(0) CIP Grayscale (1) CAS (2) Hotwire_LWC (3) SPP_200 Setup

CIP GS Data CIP GS Housekeeping CIP GS Cal Enable Enabled

COM Port 3 No Fault v2.6.5

CIP GS # Conc/LWC CIP GS Realtime Images CIP GS Selectable Charts Full Hist. Diode Voltages

Numb Conc (cts/cm ³)	0.39	Oversize Reject Count	0		
LWC (g/cm ³)	0	DOF Reject Count	0		
MVD (um)	8.33	End Reject Count	0		
ED (um)	19	Particle Counter	12		
Diode 1 V	2.4	Diode 32 V	2.47	Diode 64 V	2.55

CIP GS LWC

CIP Grayscale Particle Counter

CIP GS # Conc

Sampling Recording Read a File

Display Range 00 d 11:15:29 All

(0) CIP Grayscale (1) CAS (2) Hotwire_LWC (3) SPP_200 Setup

Enable Enabled Save Config Get DAT Observed 1.30545 Dry Air Term (g/m^3) 0.00022939 Dry Air Term (W) v2.5.1 No Fault

Hotwire_LWC Data

LWC - DAT Calc (g/m^3)

0.151

LWC - DAT Obs (g/m^3)

-0.009

P Total (W)

0

DAT Calculated (W)

0

DAT Calculated (g/m^3)

1.15

DAT Observed (W)

0

DAT Observed (g/m^3)

1.31

LWC Hotwire (V)

1.21

LWC raw (g/m^3)

1.3

LWC Slave (V)

0

Air Density (kg/m^3)

1.13

Pressure (mBar)

920.9

Airspeed (m/s)

98.1

Ambient Temp(C)

10.9

Boiling Point (K)

0

Hotwire LWC Hotwire LWC w/ DAT Selectable Charts Dual Selectable Chart Hotwire LWC Collective

1st Hotwire_LWC g/m^3

LWC - DAT Calc (g/m^3) LWC - DAT Obs (g/m^3)

In cloud R3.2

End R3.2 in cloud start P10

End P10 start R3.3 above CT

End R3.3 profile P11

CT P11

CB on P11

End P11 at 50ft start P12

End P12 start R4.1 at 500ft

Display Range

00 d 11:39:08

Occ

Enable

COM Port

v2.5.3

4

CAS Data

#Conc (#/cm ³)	Sum of Particles	LWC Hotwire (V)
1.77	973	1.09
CAS LWC (g/m ³)	Forward Overflow	LWC Slave Mon (V)
0	0	0.32
CAS MVD (um)	Backward Overflow	Laser Curr Mon (mA)
1.48	0	87.6
CAS ED(um)	Ambient Temp (C)	Laser Pwr Mon (V)
1.49	NaN	43
Dynamic Pressure	Static Pressure	Airspeed (m/s)
0	0	92.5

Standard Charts

Selectable Charts

Forward/Backscatter

CAS # Conc

Forward Scattering

Backward Scattering

CAS Volume Conc

DMT Particle Analysis and Display System

Program Configure

Sampling Recording Read a File

Display Range
All

00 d 11:41:01

0cc

(0) CIP Grayscale (1) CAS (2) Hotwire_LWC (3) SPP_200 Setup

CIP GS Data

CIP GS Housekeeping

CIP GS Cal

Enable

Enabled

COM Port 3

No Fault

v2.6.5

CIP GS # Conc/LWC

CIP GS Realtime Images

CIP GS Selectable Charts

Full Hist.

Diode Voltages

Numb Conc (cts/cm³)

0

LWC (g/cm³)

0

MWD (um)

0

ED (um)

0

Diode 1 V

2.4

Diode 32 V

2.47

Oversize Reject Count

0

DOF Reject Count

0

End Reject Count

0

Particle Counter

0

Diode 64 V

2.62

Y-axis Autoscale

X-axis Autoscale

Fully Illuminated

Dark Current

Diode Voltages

CIP Grayscale Particle Counter

End R4.1 at 500ft P13 start

CB P13

CT P13

End P13 start descent into cloud

End descent, start R4.2 in cloud at

CAS Data | CAS Housekeeping

#Conc (#/cm ³)	Sum of Particles	LWC Hotwire (V)
398.09	41365	1.32
CAS LWC (g/m ³)	Forward Overflow	LWC Slave Mon (V)
0.35	1	0.32
CAS MVD (um)	Backward Overflow	Laser Curr Mon (mA)
13.7	0	87.6
CAS ED(um)	Ambient Temp (C)	Laser Pwr Mon (V)
13.55	NaN	43
Dynamic Pressure	Static Pressure	Airspeed (m/s)
0	0	93.3

End of R4.2 (late)... CT 4400ft

End P14 start 4.3 above CT

End of P15 start of R5.1

Turning

Turn completed – crossed C130 contrail few secs ago

Flight Summary B414

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
gin	09:18:04	023	0.08kft	18.4S	70.3W						on
ASP	09:38:52	314	0.08kft	18.3S	70.3W						open
T/O	09:44:48	199	0.05kft	18.4S	70.3W						Arica
Profile 1	09:45:14	201	0.40kft	18.4S	70.3W	09:51:21	223	6.0kft	18.7S	70.5W	start as t/o 6000ft
Run 1	09:51:50	220	6.0kft	18.7S	70.6W	10:03:34	227	6.0kft	19.3S	71.2W	start as end P1
nev	09:52:22	221	6.0kft	18.7S	70.6W						zero
JW	09:53:40	227	6.0kft	18.8S	70.7W						zero
heimann	09:55:12	225	6.0kft	18.9S	70.7W						cal 09
Profile 2	10:03:34	227	6.0kft	19.3S	71.2W	10:10:28	229	-.05kft	19.6S	71.5W	50ft qnh1017
!	10:06:37	227	3.0kft	19.4S	71.3W						cloud top
!	10:06:51	225	2.8kft	19.4S	71.3W						at 3100ft
!	10:07:25	230	2.2kft	19.4S	71.4W						cloud base 2400
Profile 3	10:10:28	229	-.05kft	19.6S	71.5W	10:11:30	229	0.39kft	19.6S	71.6W	50ft qnh1017 500ft
Run 2.1	10:11:30	229	0.39kft	19.6S	71.6W	10:21:38	270	0.44kft	20.0S	72.0W	500ft
JW	10:12:42	225	0.38kft	19.6S	71.6W						zero
!	10:20:42	227	0.39kft	20.0S	72.0W						qnh 1018
Profile 4	10:21:38	270	0.44kft	20.0S	72.0W	10:22:36	268	1.4kft	20.0S	72.1W	
Run 2.2	10:22:36	268	1.4kft	20.0S	72.1W	10:27:19	267	1.4kft	20.0S	72.4W	
!	10:22:57	268	1.4kft	20.0S	72.1W						1500ft
nev	10:23:28	267	1.4kft	20.0S	72.1W						zero
JW	10:23:41	264	1.4kft	20.0S	72.2W						zero
Profile 5	10:27:20	267	1.4kft	20.0S	72.4W	10:28:50	272	2.9kft	20.0S	72.5W	
Run 2.3	10:28:50	272	2.9kft	20.0S	72.5W	10:34:16	272	2.9kft	20.0S	72.9W	
r2.3	10:29:41	266	2.9kft	20.0S	72.6W						3000ft cloud base 2700ft
Profile 6	10:34:16	272	2.9kft	20.0S	72.9W	10:36:20	269	4.8kft	20.0S	73.0W	
!	10:35:35	269	4.2kft	20.0S	73.0W						tops 3900ft
Run 2.4	10:36:20	269	4.8kft	20.0S	73.0W	10:46:50	273	4.9kft	20.0S	73.7W	
r2.4	10:36:54	268	4.9kft	20.0S	73.1W						5000ft
Profile 7	10:46:50	273	4.9kft	20.0S	73.7W	10:53:45	273	-.08kft	20.0S	74.2W	50 ft qnh1019
Profile 8	10:53:46	273	-.08kft	20.0S	74.2W	10:54:36	269	0.38kft	20.0S	74.2W	50 ft qnh1019

Profile 5	10:27:20	207	1.4kft	20.0S	72.4W	10:28:50	272	2.9kft	20.0S	72.5W	
Run 2.3	10:28:50	272	2.9kft	20.0S	72.5W	10:34:16	272	2.9kft	20.0S	72.9W	
r2.3	10:29:41	266	2.9kft	20.0S	72.6W						3000ft cloud base 2700ft
Profile 6	10:34:16	272	2.9kft	20.0S	72.9W	10:36:20	269	4.8kft	20.0S	73.0W	
l	10:35:35	269	4.2kft	20.0S	73.0W						tops 3900ft
Run 2.4	10:36:20	269	4.8kft	20.0S	73.0W	10:46:50	273	4.9kft	20.0S	73.7W	
r2.4	10:36:54	268	4.9kft	20.0S	73.1W						5000ft
Profile 7	10:46:50	273	4.9kft	20.0S	73.7W	10:53:45	273	-.08kft	20.0S	74.2W	50 ft qnh1019
Profile 8	10:53:46	273	-.08kft	20.0S	74.2W	10:54:36	269	0.38kft	20.0S	74.2W	50 ft qnh1019
Run 3.1	10:54:36	269	0.38kft	20.0S	74.2W	11:04:39	269	0.36kft	20.0S	74.9W	
r3.1	10:55:13	268	0.44kft	20.0S	74.3W						500ft
Profile 9	11:04:39	269	0.36kft	20.0S	74.9W	11:07:52	265	3.6kft	20.0S	75.1W	
Run 3.2	11:07:52	265	3.6kft	20.0S	75.1W	11:18:11	273	3.4kft	20.0S	75.7W	
l	11:08:30	263	3.5kft	20.0S	75.1W						r3.2 reset to 3600ft
Profile 10	11:18:12	273	3.4kft	20.0S	75.7W	11:19:20	272	4.4kft	20.0S	75.8W	
Run 3.3	11:19:20	272	4.4kft	20.0S	75.8W	11:30:02	274	4.5kft	20.0S	76.5W	
r3.3	11:19:46	267	4.4kft	20.0S	75.8W						500ft above cloud
heimann	11:24:04	276	4.5kft	20.1S	76.1W						cal 06
Profile 11	11:30:02	274	4.5kft	20.0S	76.5W	11:35:59	267	-.08kft	20.0S	76.9W	50ft qnh 1019
Profile 12	11:36:00	267	-.10kft	20.0S	76.9W	11:36:44	270	0.33kft	20.0S	76.9W	50ft qnh 1019
Run 4.1	11:36:44	270	0.33kft	20.0S	76.9W	11:46:49	267	0.33kft	20.0S	77.6W	
heimann	11:38:18	267	0.33kft	20.0S	77.0W						cal 09
r4.1	11:38:30	266	0.33kft	20.0S	77.1W						500ft
JW	11:38:56	266	0.34kft	20.0S	77.1W						zero check
nev	11:39:10	267	0.38kft	20.0S	77.1W						zero check
Profile 13	11:46:49	267	0.33kft	20.0S	77.6W	11:51:19	271	4.0kft	20.0S	77.9W	
Run 4.2	11:51:19	271	4.0kft	20.0S	77.9W	12:01:26	264	4.0kft	20.0S	78.6W	
p13	11:52:12	269	4.0kft	20.0S	77.9W						pop up above to check cloud top
Profile 14	12:01:27	262	4.0kft	20.0S	78.6W	12:02:35	271	4.9kft	20.0S	78.6W	
Run 4.3	12:02:36	271	4.9kft	20.0S	78.6W	12:15:09	270	4.9kft	20.0S	79.5W	
Profile 15	12:15:09	270	4.9kft	20.0S	79.5W	12:16:04	273	5.4kft	19.9S	79.5W	
Run 5.1	12:16:18	274	5.4kft	19.9S	79.5W						
r5.1	12:19:16	091	5.3kft	20.0S	79.5W						C130 run start 1 mile south of C130 track

End run 5.1 P16 down

P16 CT at 4600ft (Capt)

End P16 start R5.2

R5.2 cf with CVI LA 0.1g m-3

End R5.2 start P17

P17 end R5.3 at 500ft started 124531

Display Range
All

00 d 12:50:46

OCC

Enable Enabled

COM Port
4 v2.5.3

CAS Data CAS Housekeeping

#Conc (#/cm ³)	Sum of Particles	LWC Hotwire (V)
1.85	814	1.09
CAS LWC (g/m ³)	Forward Overflow	LWC Slave Mon (V)
0	0	0.32
CAS MVD (um)	Backward Overflow	Laser Curr Mon (mA)
8.75	0	87.5
CAS ED(um)	Ambient Temp (C)	Laser Pwr Mon (V)
5.71	NaN	43
Dynamic Pressure	Static Pressure	Airspeed (m/s)
0	0	88.6

Standard Charts Selectable Charts Forward/Backscatter

Forward Scattering Backward Scattering

End R5.3 at 500ft start P18 to FL230

Display Range: 00 d 12:35:25 OCC

Enable Enabled

COM Port: 4 v2.5.3

#Conc (#/cm ³)	Sum of Particles	LWC Hotwire (V)
529.42	48970	1.53
CAS LWC (g/m ³)	Forward Overflow	LWC Slave Mon (V)
0.65	0	0.32
CAS MVD (um)	Backward Overflow	Laser Curr Mon (mA)
15.66	0	87.5
CAS ED(um)	Ambient Temp (C)	Laser Pwr Mon (V)
15.55	NaN	43
Dynamic Pressure	Static Pressure	Airspeed (m/s)
0	0	91.8

Just after end of P18 Start R6 at FL230

DS1

DS2

DS3

DS4

DS5

DS6

DS7

R6 end start P19 at FL230

Display Range

00 d 14:36:16

OCC

Enable Enabled

COM Port v2.5.3

4

CAS Data CAS Housekeeping

#Conc (#/cm ³)	Sum of Particles	LWC Hotwire (V)
0.04	30	0.96
CAS LWC (g/m ³)	Forward Overflow	LWC Slave Mon (V)
0	0	0.32
CAS MVD (um)	Backward Overflow	Laser Curr Mon (mA)
0.92	0	87.7
CAS ED(um)	Ambient Temp (C)	Laser Pwr Mon (V)
0.93	NaN	43.1
Dynamic Pressure	Static Pressure	Airspeed (m/s)
0	0	107.1

CAS # Conc

CAS Volume Conc

Inc in scatt when humidity inc

P19 int

Flight B414 14:46:47
Heading 48 deg Speed 231 knots Height 7.0kft Press 781mb
Lat 18°42.0'S Long 70°30.0'W Wind 1 ms-1/71 deg
Temp 14.1C Dewpoint -1.62C
From 09:19:17 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -70.55 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE -18.7 deg (+ve N)

Run 4.1	11:36:44	270	0.33kft	20.0S	76.9W	11:46:49	267	0.33kft	20.0S	77.6W	
heimann	11:38:18	267	0.33kft	20.0S	77.0W						cal 09
r4.1	11:38:30	266	0.33kft	20.0S	77.1W						500ft
JW	11:38:56	266	0.34kft	20.0S	77.1W						zero check
nev	11:39:10	267	0.38kft	20.0S	77.1W						zero check
Profile 13	11:46:49	267	0.33kft	20.0S	77.6W	11:51:19	271	4.0kft	20.0S	77.9W	
Run 4.2	11:51:19	271	4.0kft	20.0S	77.9W	12:01:26	264	4.0kft	20.0S	78.6W	
p13	11:52:12	269	4.0kft	20.0S	77.9W						pop up above to check cloud top
Profile 14	12:01:27	262	4.0kft	20.0S	78.6W	12:02:35	271	4.9kft	20.0S	78.6W	
Run 4.3	12:02:36	271	4.9kft	20.0S	78.6W	12:15:09	270	4.9kft	20.0S	79.5W	
Profile 15	12:15:09	270	4.9kft	20.0S	79.5W	12:16:04	273	5.4kft	19.9S	79.5W	
Run 5.1	12:16:18	274	5.4kft	19.9S	79.5W	12:30:34	093	5.4kft	20.0S	78.8W	
r5.1	12:19:16	091	5.3kft	20.0S	79.5W						C130 run start 1 mile south of C130 track
Profile 16	12:30:35	093	5.4kft	20.0S	78.8W	12:31:57	087	4.2kft	20.0S	78.7W	
Run 5.2	12:31:57	087	4.2kft	20.0S	78.7W	12:41:46	096	4.2kft	20.0S	78.1W	
Profile 17	12:41:46	096	4.2kft	20.0S	78.1W	12:45:30	097	0.33kft	20.0S	77.9W	
Run 5.3	12:45:31	097	0.33kft	20.0S	77.9W	12:55:34	094	0.38kft	20.0S	77.3W	
r5.3	12:46:12	094	0.34kft	20.0S	77.8W						qnh 1020
Profile 18	12:56:15	047	1.1kft	20.0S	77.3W	13:16:26	058	23.0kft	20.1S	78.3W	start as end r5,3
Run 6	13:16:26	058	23.0kft	20.1S	78.3W	14:25:08	039	22.9kft	19.8S	71.7W	
Sonde 1	13:19:24	082	23.0kft	20.0S	78.0W						
Heimann	13:25:08	092	23.0kft	20.0S	77.4W						cal 06
Sonde 2	13:29:43	098	23.0kft	20.0S	77.0W						
Sonde 3	13:39:50	091	23.0kft	20.0S	76.0W						
Sonde 4	13:50:15	093	23.0kft	20.0S	75.0W						
Sonde 5	14:00:40	096	23.0kft	20.0S	74.0W						
Sonde 6	14:11:13	088	23.0kft	20.0S	73.0W						
Sonde 7	14:21:21	090	22.9kft	20.0S	72.0W						
Profile 19	14:25:08	039	22.9kft	19.8S	71.7W						
p19	14:43:09	054	7.0kft	18.9S	70.7W						interrupted fl070

Chemistry Log

Date: 04 Nov 2008

Flight: B414

Operator: Doug Anderson / Guy Gratton

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Preflight

No.	? or x	Location	Action	Comments
Gases				
1	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
2	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	173
3	X	Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
4	X	Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	45
5	X	CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
6	X	CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	24 CO time synch @ 07:35:00
Flows				
7	X	Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 07. LPM on both channels	
8	X	NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	X	NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	X	CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	X	CO pressure cell	~ 7.5 bar	
12	X	CO pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	
Zeros				
13	X	Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
14	X	NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
15	X	CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	08:39:02 to 09:08:16
16	X	SO ₂ zero (not for most flights)	Left for approx 10 min	
Other				
17	X	Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
18	X	HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
19	No	CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	
TDLAS				
20	n/a	230V	230V power breakers on	
21	n/a	28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
22	n/a	Laptop	On and software working	
23	n/a	Data	Being saved to correct directories	

Post flight

Switch Off				
1	X	CO	Switch off instrument	
2	X	Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	X	NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	X	Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	X	Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
Gases (note pressures)				
6	X	CO ₂ /Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	175
7	X	CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	45
8	X	Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling	15
Driers				
9	X	Small drier	Change if spent	
10	X	Large drier	Change if spent	
TDLAS				
11	n/a	Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	n/a	Laptop	Shut down	
13	n/a	Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
Log				
14	X	Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	None	Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	n/a	TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

Chemistry Log

Date: 04 Nov 2008

Flight: B414

Operator: Doug Anderson / Guy Gratton

Page 2 of 2

In flight

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.
During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
08:07:11	Ground, pre power c/o	82.95	314.53	26090.17	35.51	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
09:18:10	Ground, pre power c/o	91.18	311.30	28384.50	40.50	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
09:34:40	Ground, pre power c/o	91.10	313.12	28524.00	40.54	7.54
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
09:41:42	Ground, during taxi	91.73	310.35	28467.83	40.53	7.53
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)

Flight level	Zero Start time	Zero End time	Counts (Hz)	Span Start time	Span End time	Conc. Range	Counts range	Pressure Cell (Torr)	Lamp Temp	O3 Intensities
6000'	09:52:40	09:53:40	27770 - 28367	09:53:45	09:54:45	504 - 514	74583 - 75592	7.49	40.53	A: 109577 B: 131804
3000'	10:29:16	10:30:20	28028 - 28151	10:30:35	10:31:35	506 - 517	74952 - 76097	7.51	40.47	A: 96954 B: 116572
3800'	11:08:40	11:09:40	27935 - 28552	11:09:45	11:10:40	522 - 536	75800 - 76900	7.54	39.51	A: 94475 B: 113548
4000'	11:51:17	11:52:40	28045 - 28724	11:52:40	1:53:45	520 - 531		7.50	38.88	A: 93410 B: 112313
Zero and cal valves both on between 11:52:25 and 11:52:40										
500'	12:45:30	11:46:30	27776- 28340	11:46:30	11:48:32	526 - 533		7.53	38.51	A: 93201 B: 112059
23,000	13:25:00	13:25:40	27660-28524	13:26:00	13:26:40	518-537	75990-76500	7.34	39.04	A: B:
23,000	14:05:00	14:05:40	27267-28070	14:06:00	14:06:40	507-521	75440-76527	7.36	40.50	A:94788 B:114102
8,000	14:39:00	14:39:40	27358-28100	14:40:40	14:40:40	507-515	74914-75636	7.52	40.50	A:95015 B:114350
Just after removal of vent cap										

O3 Intensity						
Time	Flight level	O3 A Intensity	O3 B Intensity			
09:42:12	Taxi	112063	134947			
09:44:15	T/o	112480	135423			
09:45:50	1000'	112680	135672			
09:47:10	?	112722	135727			
09:50:	?	112211	135072			

In flight comments

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 414

Date: 4/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
09:46:49	6400	0.07	2													FL020	
09:47:45	3400	0.07	58													FL030	
09:49:16	900	0.07														FL040	
09:50:25	1000	0.07														FL050	
09:51:30	400	0.07														End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1 @ FL060	
09:52:00	410	0.07															
09:54:00	500	0.07															
09:56:00	450	0.08															
09:58:00	430	0.06															
10:00:00	330	0.07															
10:02:00	500	0.07															
10:03:40	460	0.07														End of Run & Start Profile 2	
10:04:38	680	0.07	59													FL050	
10:05:35	900	0.07														FL040	
10:06:30	1000	0.07														FL030	
10:07:40	3500	0.07	85													FL020	
10:08:33	4800	0.07														FL010	
10:09:28	2600	0.07														End of Profile 2 & Start Profile 3 @ 50'	
10:11:30	2300	0.07														End of Profile 3 & Start Run 2.1 @ 500'	
10:12:00	2300	0.07															
10:14:00	2100	0.07															
10:16:00	2500	0.07															
10:18:00	2000	0.07															
10:20:00	1900	0.07															
10:22:39																End of Run 2.1 & Start Profile 4	
10:22:19	1900	0.07														FL010	
10:22:36																End of Profile 4 & Start Run 2.2 @ 1500'	
10:23:00	2000	0.07															
10:25:00	1900	0.07															
10:27:20																End of Run & Start Profile 5	
10:28:50																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 2.3 @ FL029	
10:29:00	1100	0.19	237			5	100	350	14			0.25	175	13	0.2	12	
10:31:00	400	0.15	353			2	100	300	10			0.15	150	10	0.1	12	
10:33:00	2000	0.07															
10:34:17																End of Run & Start Profile 6	
10:35:34	980															FL040	
10:36:21			Fail													End of Profile 6 & Start Run 2.4 @ FL049	
10:39:00	800	0.07															
10:41:00	500	0.07															
10:43:00	500	0.07															
10:45:00	550	0.07															
10:46:49																End of Run & Start Profile 7	
10:47:56	600	0.11														FL040	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.6 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 414

Date: 4/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
10:49:00	700	0.18	121			6		400	18			0.7	125	15	0.17	FL030	
10:50:15	2000	0.07	124													FL020	
10:51:25	2300	0.07														FL010	
10:53:44	2700	0.07														End of P7 & Start P8 from 50'	
10:54:35																End of P8 @ 500' & Start Run 3.1 @ 500'	
10:55:00	3600	0.07															
10:57:00	3000	0.07															
10:59:00	3000	0.07															
11:01:00	2800	0.07	125														
11:03:00	3100	0.07															
11:04:39																End of Run & Start Profile 9	
11:05:33	3450	0.07														FL010	
11:06:40	3200	0.07														FL020	
11:07:12	3100	0.07														FL030	
11:07:56																End of Profile & Start Run 3.2 @ 3600'	
11:08:00	1800	0.18	Fail			2	100	400	10			0.1	250	12	0.2	12	
11:12:00	1400	0.09	232			2		500	12			0.05	200	11	0.1	12	
11:14:00	1200	0.12	240			2		400	12			0.05	225	11	0.15	12	
11:16:00	1300	0.09	500			1	75	500	11			0.05	250	11	0.15	12	
11:18:18																End of Run & Start P10	
11:18:59	1000	0.09	713													FL040	
11:19:44																End of P10 & Start Run 3.3 @ FL044	
11:20:00	500	0.08															
11:22:00	200	0.06															
11:24:00	220	0.07															
11:26:00	230	0.07															
11:28:00	290	0.07															
11:30:03																End of Run Start Profile 11	
11:30:44	1300	0.09	727			1		400	10				125	11	0.06	12	
11:32:47	2300	0.09	754													FL020	
11:33:51	2400	0.08														FL010	
11:35:59	3000	0.07														End of Profile 11 & Start Profile 12 @ 50'	
11:36:44																End of P12 & Start Run 4.1 @ 500'	
11:37:00	2800	0.07															
11:39:00	2600	0.07															
11:41:00	2600	0.07															
11:43:00	2600	0.07															
11:45:00	2500	0.07															
11:46:47																End of Run 4.1 & Start P13	
11:47:38	2400	0.07														FL010	
11:48:34	2300	0.07														FL020	
11:49:25	2230	0.07														FL030	
11:50:17																End of P13 & Start Run 4.2 @ 4100'	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.6 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 414

Date: 4/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:52:00	2100	0.19	876			4	125	250	15			0.15	160	15	0.2	12	
11:54:00	1900	0.14	1060			3	100	350	14			0.15	160	15	0.2	12	
11:56:00	2400	0.16	1239			3	250	350	15			0.25	160	15	0.2	12	
11:58:00	5400	0.12	1415			2	100	300	15			0.25	160	15	0.3	12	
12:00:00	3000	0.17	1572			1		300	15			0.25	160	15	0.25	12	
12:01:26																	End of Run & Start Profile 14
12:02:34																	End of Profile 5000' & Start Run 4.3
12:03:00	800	0.06	1726														
12:04:00	540	0.07															
12:06:00	750	0.07															
12:08:00	610	0.07															
12:10:00	500	0.07															
12:12:00	300	0.07															
12:14:00	340	0.07															
12:15:10																	End of Run 4.3 & Start Profile 15
12:15:44																	End of P 15 & Start Run 5.1
12:18:00	260	0.07															
12:20:00	360	0.07															
12:22:00	270	0.07	1727														
12:24:00	220	0.07															
12:26:00	350	0.07															
12:28:00	500	0.07															
12:30:00	140	0.10															
12:30:36																	End of Run & Start Profile 16
12:31:57																	End of Profile 16 & Start Run 5.2 @ FL041
12:32:00	1200	0.20	1802			4	125	200	18			0.4	125	17	0.4	12	
12:34:00	2800	0.20	1899			8	200	100	18			0.4	150	20	0.4	1	
12:36:00	4700	0.19	2120			2	100	200	18			0.25	150	17	0.4	12	
12:38:00	4400	0.17	2300			2	100	250	18			0.3	150	20	0.5	12	
12:40:00	5400	0.15	2478			2	150	250	18			0.2	150	17	0.4	12	
12:41:45																	End of Run 5.2 & Start Profile 17
12:42:53	3600	0.06	2707														FL030
12:43:50	4000	0.07															FL020
12:44:59	3900	0.06															FL010
12:45:31																	End of P17 & Start Run 5.3 @ 500'
12:46:00	3700	0.06															
12:48:00	3500	0.07															
12:50:00	3600	0.07															
12:52:00	3200	0.07															
12:54:00	3040	0.07															
12:55:34																	End of Run 5.4 & Start P18
12:56:26	2500	0.07															FL010
12:57:00	2400	0.07															FL020

PCASP Reference Volts = 7V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.6 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

Size	#	changed	Flight/date	discharged	Comments.
10	1 } 2 }	3/11 ICNB	B414/ 4/11	4/11	
10	3 } 4 }	3/11 ICNB	B414 4/11	4/11	
10	7 } 8 }	3/11 ICNB	NOT USED 4/11	4/11	
10	10 } 69 }	3/11 ICNB	B414 4/11	4/11	← put hole in filler with finger at discharge
10	21 } 23 }	3/11 ICNB	NOT USED 4/11	-	(Clean glove touched filler surface on 21 3/11)
10	33 } 40 }	3/11 ICNB	NOT USED 4/11	-	

Filter #	Loc'n	T _{ON}	T _{OFF}	RUN	V.L.	Tot
1,2	L	101301	102135	R2.1	567	-
1,2	L	105508	110430	R3.1	559	1126
10,69	L	123347	123922	R5.2	Blank	0
3,4	L	103728	114643	R4.1	562	-
	L	124640	125534	R5.3	597	1159

B4114

C130 intercomparison runs

Flight:

B414

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B414

Date: 04/11/08

Instruments

RFC	condensation running on inside of window, avalon informed
Filters	ok
Dropsondes	7 dropped, all ok & satcommed
CVI -	ok
Neph -PSAP - wetNeph	ok
AMS	ok
Core Chem -	ok
Cloud physics -	PCASP - leak near inlet jet?
ARIES -	ok
MARSS -	ok
SWS -	ok
SHIMS	upper ok, lower intermittant
CCN -	single channel only, data recording started late due pc problems. Shut down early in profile to fl230
VACC -	ok
2DS -	ok
CAPS -	ok
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	experimental operation

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

MPDS
Run for flight

Satcom-H Calls
nil

Issues

CVI log

11/4/08 9:52:20 AM lyman zero and back to sample
11/4/08 9:53:21 AM aerosol mode.
11/4/08 10:06:42 AM cloud
11/4/08 10:07:05 AM aerosol mode for transition (10sec)
11/4/08 10:22:10 AM cf of ready for 1500 ft set up
11/4/08 10:22:15 AM cf of ready for 1500 ft set up
11/4/08 10:23:29 AM ams on
11/4/08 10:23:39 AM
11/4/08 10:24:30 AM
11/4/08 10:25:25 AM
11/4/08 10:26:44 AM
11/4/08 10:27:28 AM CVI set for just above zero
11/4/08 10:28:23 AM ams flow set at 0.5 cf cntl 0.7 flow diff .2lpm
11/4/08 10:28:27 AM ams flow set at 0.5 cf cntl 0.7 flow diff .2lpm
11/4/08 10:28:39 AM cloud
11/4/08 10:32:19 AM cf down to 0.5 to increase water content
11/4/08 10:32:53 AM out of cloud
11/4/08 10:36:05 AM Above cloud run. Aerosol mode.
11/4/08 10:45:39 AM AMS still samplinf of CVI in aerosol mode for the first above cloud run
11/4/08 10:46:22 AM dial for ams at zero as didn't know AMS was sampling.
11/4/08 10:46:52 AM AMS going back to rosemount for profile down
11/4/08 10:48:15 AM cloud
11/4/08 10:49:26 AM out of cloud base
11/4/08 11:04:38 AM cf mode for cloud run
11/4/08 11:05:01 AM AMS on cvi
11/4/08 11:05:07 AM AMS on cvi
11/4/08 11:06:34 AM AMS on cvi
11/4/08 11:07:26 AM ams flow dial to .49 cf cntl at 0,5 diff =0.1
11/4/08 11:11:44 AM ams flow dial to .49 cf cntl at 0,5 diff =0.1
11/4/08 11:12:38 AM ams flow dial to .49 cf cntl at 0,5 diff =0.1
11/4/08 11:13:09 AM ams flow dial to .48 cf cntl at 0,4 diff =0.05 to .1
11/4/08 11:13:56 AM
11/4/08 11:14:09 AM ams dial to 0.4lpm
11/4/08 11:15:48 AM ams dial to 0.3lpm
11/4/08 11:16:11 AM ams dial to 0.3lpm
11/4/08 11:20:25 AM Aerosol mode
11/4/08 11:34:02 AM aerosol mode for decent.
11/4/08 11:47:20 AM cf on ready for cloud run
11/4/08 11:48:15 AM AMS switching to cvi, use 0.3lpm and cf cntl=0.4
11/4/08 11:50:05 AM cf diff =0.8 to 0.1 slight noice on zero.
11/4/08 11:55:09 AM hygro dilution to 0.2
11/4/08 11:56:32 AM hygro dilution to 0.3
11/4/08 11:56:56 AM hygro dilution to 0.3
11/4/08 11:57:10 AM Cf to 0.1 control
11/4/08 11:57:19 AM Cf to 0.1 control
11/4/08 11:57:53 AM cf dif 0.01 to 0.05
11/4/08 12:01:23 PM hygro shows no difference to new cf cntrol or dillution factor.
11/4/08 12:02:30 PM above cloud ams to rose mounts
11/4/08 12:02:50 PM aerosol mode
11/4/08 12:20:52 PM PCASP flow tweeked up.
11/4/08 12:27:58 PM cf mode on
11/4/08 12:29:06 PM cf mode on NOams, still good zero with control at 0.1
11/4/08 12:29:44 PM CVI onlone, cf diffs of 0.02
11/4/08 12:31:36 PM AMS to CVI
11/4/08 12:31:44 PM in cloud
11/4/08 12:42:44 PM out of cloud base,AMS to rosemounts.
11/4/08 12:43:53 PM aerosol mode
11/4/08 12:56:11 PM climbing for sondes at 23000. Aerosol mode left on.
11/4/08 12:58:30 PM cloud
11/4/08 3:11:09 PM hygro to zero sample (not zero'ed)

ARIES flight log

Flight: B414

page 1 of 2

Date: 04/Nov/2008

Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
~0800	Power on.						
0801	—		CH	C	71	37	Cold Hot min. script CBB overrun?
083245	—		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot min.
0945	TAKE OFF						
0957	6000ft		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3min script Ci above
095930			N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 30sec 7/8 SCU below
100375	P↓			C	71	31	6000ft → 5000ft
101127	R2.1 500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30sec (1)
1021				O	71	31	Banking
102138	P↑			O	71	31	
102236	R2.2 1500ft			O	71	31	
102720	P↑			C	71	30	End of script (1)
103620	R2.4 5000		NZ	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3min Cloud above Ci ^{some}
104628		60x1	N	C	71	31	Nadir Profile start near end
104650	P↓						
104717			CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot min.
105440	R2.1 500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30sec. End 11:04
100434	P↑		—	C	71	31	500ft → 3800ft
111930	500ft above cloud		Z	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long 3min. Ci + more above
112800			N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3min Brake cloud below.
113000	↓			C	71	31	
113043			CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot min.
113644	500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30sec.
114649	P↑		—	C	71	31	—
120156	5000ft		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3min Above 8/8 SCU Below Ci etc.
1214			N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3min
121556			Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3min Turn below Z!
122133			N	O	71	30	Nadir Long Run 3min Ci above 8/8 SCU below
122542			Z	O	70	30	Zenith Long Run 3min
1230	End ↓		—	C	71	31	
124510	↓ R2.3 500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30sec.

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	4/11/08	Flight	B414	log pages
Operator(s)	Jeff Norwood-Brown		Campaign	VOCALS		
Departure			Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	0752
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	21.3°C	Ch 17	21.4°C	Ch18	20.2°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	0753
Initial target temperatures	Hot	292.3	Cold	291.5		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	0757
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.57	Cold	292.71	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

Flight #	B414	Date	4/11/08	Operator(s)	JNB	log page	2	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
0840			Happy that all is well. Switching off MARSS pod until needed.						
0915			MARSS pod back on						
0925			T/O will be start of profile 1						
094448	P1↑	0	Start of profile under presumably 8/8 Sc5 though it's very dark and hard to tell.						
094658	P1↑	FL020	Into cloud						
094748	P1↑	FL028	Above 8/8 Sc5 3/8 Ac3 above and 4/8 Ci1 above that						
095120	1	FL060	Above mist (8/8 thin St1) layer but SC5 edge now behind us. 4/8 Ac3 above with 5/8 Ci1 above that						
095738	1	FL060	Back above 7/8 SC5 layer						
100334	P2↓	FL060	Start of profile descent to 50ft. Above 7/8 Sc5 below 4/8 Ac3 and 3/8 Ci1						
100644	P2↓	FL031	Entered Sc5 layer						
100720	P2↓	FL024	Below Sc5 though further 2/8 St7 (or St Fractus as drizzle noted by Cptn) at around FL011						
101028	P3↑	50ft	Start of profile to FL005						
101130	2	FL005	Start or run below 2/8 St7 and 8/8 Sc5						
102138	P4↑	FL005	Start of profile climb below 7/8 Sc5						
102236	2.2	FL015	Start of run below 7/8 Sc5 heading W along 20 th S parallel						
102720	P5↑	FL015	Profile climb up to FL030 into 8/8 Sc5 layer for in cloud run						
102850	2.3	FL030	Start of in cloud run						
103416	P6↑	FL030	Start of profile climb to FL050						
103620	2.4	FL050	Start of above cloud run. 8/8 Sc5 below 1/8 Ac3 and 6/8 Ci1						
1045	2.4	FL050	Ci is Ci2 in places so 4/8 Ci1 2/8 Ci2						
104650	P7↓	FL050	Profile descent to 50ft – no change in cloud amounts or type						
104809	P7↓	FL041	Into 8/8 Sc5						
104944	P7↓	FL025	Below 8/8 Sc5 no sign of St7 (or St6 fractus) this far out (73° 54.0'W)						
105346	P8↑	50ft	Profile climb to FL005						
105436	3.1	FL005	Start of run below 8/8 Sc5						
110154	3.1	FL005	Layer now 7/8 Sc5 above						
110439	P9↑	FL005	Start of profile climb to FL038						
110752	3.2	FL038	Start of run in cloud tops						
110830	3.2	FL036	Run reset to FL036 in order to be in cloud middles						
111812	P10↑	FL036	Start of profile to – 8/8 Sc5 below 4/8 Ci2 2/8 Ci1						
111920	3.3	FL045	Start or above cloud run clouds remain as above						
1126	3.3	FL045	Sc5 layer now 7/8						
113002	P11↓	FL045	Start of profile to 50ft						
113102	P11↓	FL038	Into 7/8 Sc5 layer						
113155	P11↓	FL030	Below 7/8 Sc5						
113600	P12↑	50ft	Start of profile to FL005						

B414_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

07:47:42.51 --- - - - -
07:47:42.51 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:47:42.51 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:47:42.51 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B414
07:47:42.51 --- - - - -
07:47:51.25 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
07:47:54.01 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
07:47:54.56 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
07:47:58.80 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:48:03.55 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:48:07.12 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:48:08.00 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:48:08.51 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:48:09.86 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:48:14.15 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:48:21.86 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:48:21.86 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:48:23.98 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:48:27.33 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:48:27.33 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:48:29.62 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:48:32.76 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:48:32.77 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:48:35.95 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:48:35.95 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:48:35.96 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:48:46.13 SWS - - - - Idling
07:48:46.14 USH - - - - Idling
07:48:46.25 LSH - - - - Idling
07:49:19.78 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:49:20.61 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:49:26.23 LSH - - - - Idling
07:49:36.94 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
07:49:38.60 SWS 170.4 - - - - Telescope stopped.
09:11:27.34 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:11:27.35 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:11:27.36 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:11:32.98 USH - - - - Idling
09:11:32.98 SWS - - - - Idling
09:11:33.41 USH - - - - Idling
09:11:33.42 SWS - - - - Idling
09:11:33.42 LSH - - - - Idling
09:11:42.94 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
09:47:46.84 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
09:47:47.98 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
09:47:50.83 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:47:50.83 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:47:50.84 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:47:58.68 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:48:05.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:48:05.69 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:48:05.79 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:48:07.13 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:48:07.37 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:48:12.54 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:05.02 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:05.04 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:05.14 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:06.50 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:06.68 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:09.12 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:09.17 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:10.62 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:10.78 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:11.90 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:52:42.53 --- - - - - *** cirrus above

```

09:53:01.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** firs t run
09:53:31.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** above brokrn srat0cumulus sheet below
09:54:08.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
09:59:51.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:00:16.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:00:52.09	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:00:53.81	SWS	172.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:02:22.22	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:02:23.92	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:03:18.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:03:39.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:06:49.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3100 ft
10:09:49.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:10:29.35	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:10:31.06	SWS	172.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:13:08.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:13:12.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:12.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:12.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:14.00	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:13:15.76	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:13:17.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:17.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:17.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:44.30	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:13:48.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:48.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:48.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:49.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:49.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:50.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:50.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:54.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:56.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:05.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:05.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:05.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:06.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:07.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:09.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:09.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:10.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:10.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:11.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:11.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:12.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:12.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:12.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:19.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:19.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:19.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:03.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:03.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:03.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:10.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:10.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:10.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:12.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:12.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:17.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:18.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:18.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:18.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:19.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:20.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:23.45	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:18:23.46	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:18:24.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:26.73	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.

10:18:26.74	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:18:28.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:28.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:28.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:29.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:30.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:31.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:31.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:32.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:32.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:35.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:40.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:40.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:40.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:41.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:21:53.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 4 climbing
10:22:50.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run at 1500 ft run 2.2
10:24:26.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:26.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:26.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:26.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:32.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:32.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:32.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:33.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:34.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:39.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:39.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:39.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:39.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:40.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:41.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:46.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:50.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:50.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:50.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:20.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:27:29.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 5
10:28:47.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** going into cloud
10:28:51.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
10:29:20.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud 2.,3 at 3000 ft cloud base is at 2700 ft
10:30:22.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:22.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:22.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:30.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:31.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:32.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:32.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:37.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:38.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:39.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:40.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:41.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:45.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:46.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:47.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:47.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:49.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:50.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:56.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:56.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:36.44	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:31:38.12	SWS	171.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:31:58.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:32:54.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base has lifted here now skimming in and out of cloud
10:32:59.94	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:33:01.69	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

10:33:43.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:34:13.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:34:21.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
10:36:21.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** above cloud run
10:36:46.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirrus above
10:38:01.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:01.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:01.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:04.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:04.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:04.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:05.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:06.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:11.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:11.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:11.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:11.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:12.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:13.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:18.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:19.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:19.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:19.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:20.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:41:43.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:44:16.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:45:29.01	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:45:30.74	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:46:50.79	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:46:52.50	SWS	-3.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:47:10.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 7 descending to low alt
10:48:02.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** going into cloud
10:49:19.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** leaving cloud CT 4100 ft
10:49:33.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 2900 ft
10:53:45.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft
10:53:49.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:54:36.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** run below cloud at 500 ft
10:54:47.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3.1`
10:55:03.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:09.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:16.86	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
10:55:16.87	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
10:55:20.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:22.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:26.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:26.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:26.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:26.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:41.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:41.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:41.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:42.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:42.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:43.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:44.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:44.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:44.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:44.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:45.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:45.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:46.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:46.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:46.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:47.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:47.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:48.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:53.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:53.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:53.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:01:37.19	---	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:02:04.18	---	-	-	-	*** broken cloud above
11:03:47.80	---	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:04:40.41	---	-	-	-	*** end of run profile climb
11:04:54.62	---	-	-	-	*** profile 9
11:06:18.45	---	-	-	-	***
11:06:18.47	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:18.49	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:18.55	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:24.66	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:24.66	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:24.67	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:25.50	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:25.96	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:26.34	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:26.91	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:26.91	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:26.93	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:27.81	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:28.25	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:28.60	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:28.87	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:28.88	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:28.89	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:29.94	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:30.18	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:30.36	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:36.14	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:36.14	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:36.16	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:47.95	---	-	-	-	*** in cloud
11:07:59.75	---	-	-	-	*** above cloud
11:08:13.40	---	-	-	-	*** dropping into cloud agsain
11:08:20.22	---	-	-	-	*** cloud base 3200 ft
11:08:53.79	---	-	-	-	*** in cloud run at 3600 ft run 3.2
11:09:24.74	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:24.76	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:24.85	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:32.17	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:32.18	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:32.21	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:33.29	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:33.45	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:33.63	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:36.25	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:36.26	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:36.27	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:37.11	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:37.52	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:37.92	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:38.67	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:38.68	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:38.69	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:39.72	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:39.96	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:40.14	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:45.31	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:45.31	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:45.34	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:49.64	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:49.69	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:49.71	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:57.14	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:57.15	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:57.17	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:58.01	USH	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:58.42	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:58.84	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:59.54	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:14:59.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:59.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:00.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:00.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:01.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:08.96	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:15:10.69	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:15:11.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:11.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:11.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:54.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:17:16.93	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:17:18.69	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:18:12.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
11:18:21.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 10
11:18:50.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** above cloud now
11:19:57.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run above strat and below cirrus
11:20:02.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3.3
11:22:01.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:22:24.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:24.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:24.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:30.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:30.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:30.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:31.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:31.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:31.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:31.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:32.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:32.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:32.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:32.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:32.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:32.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:33.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:34.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:34.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:37.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:37.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:37.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:38.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:39.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:39.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:39.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:39.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:39.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:40.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:40.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:43.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:43.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:10.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** F
11:25:16.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** l 045
11:26:44.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:27:14.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:28:56.07	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:28:57.82	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:29:18.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:18.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:18.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:22.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:22.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:22.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:23.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:23.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:24.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:25.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:25.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:25.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:29:26.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:26.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:27.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:35.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:35.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:35.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:06.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
11:30:17.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
11:30:54.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** going into cloud
11:31:41.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud
11:32:28.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** when reach 50 ft view will change from nadir to zenith
11:33:12.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:36:01.00	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:36:02.74	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:36:17.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:36:49.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
11:36:53.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4.1
11:37:37.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** broken cloud above
11:38:20.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:21.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:21.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:31.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:31.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:31.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:32.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:32.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:33.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:34.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:34.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:34.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:35.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:35.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:36.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:43.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:43.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:43.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:50.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:42:37.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:46:46.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start
11:46:54.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** of profile climb
11:49:46.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** base at 3400 ft
11:50:33.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** main base 3650 ft cloud top at 4400 ft
11:51:20.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 4100 ft in cloud
11:51:30.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4.2
11:52:28.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:28.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:28.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:34.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:34.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:34.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:35.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:35.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:36.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:36.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:36.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:37.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:37.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:37.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:38.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:39.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:39.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:46.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:46.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:46.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:19.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:56:41.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:41.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:41.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:56:46.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:46.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:46.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:47.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:48.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:48.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:49.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:49.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:49.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:50.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:50.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:51.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:59.76	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:57:01.49	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:57:02.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:02.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:02.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:26.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:01:31.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:02:10.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4000 sometjing
12:02:32.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** start opf run when change to zenith
12:02:35.90	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:02:36.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:02:37.64	SWS	-5.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:02:42.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:42.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:43.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:46.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:46.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:46.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:47.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:48.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:48.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:49.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:49.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:49.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:50.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:50.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:51.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:51.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:51.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:51.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:52.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:52.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:53.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:57.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:57.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:57.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:20.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** stratocumulus below and cirrus above
12:06:02.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:10:29.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:29.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:29.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:33.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:33.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:33.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:34.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:34.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:35.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:38.46	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:10:40.21	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:10:41.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:41.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:41.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:45.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:45.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:45.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:46.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:46.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:10:46.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:47.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:47.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:48.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:53.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:53.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:53.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:35.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:13:16.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:15:11.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:15:18.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing
12:15:43.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 5500 ft
12:16:19.55	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:16:20.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:16:21.26	SWS	-5.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:16:25.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:25.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:25.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:30.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:30.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:30.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:31.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:32.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:32.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:34.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:34.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:34.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:35.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:35.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:36.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:37.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:37.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:37.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:38.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:38.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:39.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:40.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:40.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:40.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:41.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:42.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:42.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:48.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:48.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:48.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:48.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:19:08.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** C130 comparison
12:19:18.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:18.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:18.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:22.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:22.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:22.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:23.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:24.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:24.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:25.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:25.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:25.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:26.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:26.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:27.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:27.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:27.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:27.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:28.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:29.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:29.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:34.88	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000

12:19:36.63	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:19:37.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:37.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:37.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:27.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:28:25.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:25.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:25.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:28.32	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:28:30.06	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:28:32.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:32.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:32.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:42.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:42.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:42.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:47.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:47.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:47.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:47.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:48.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:48.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:50.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:50.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:50.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:50.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:51.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:51.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:56.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:56.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:56.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:30:56.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** run ended
12:31:00.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending
12:31:06.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:31:41.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
12:31:48.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4600 ft
12:32:03.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** run in cloud
12:32:38.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:32:52.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:52.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:52.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:57.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:57.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:57.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:58.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:58.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:58.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:59.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:59.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:59.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:00.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:01.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:01.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:02.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:02.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:02.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:03.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:03.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:04.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:11.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:11.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:11.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:16.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:16.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:16.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:16.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:21.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:21.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:21.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:35:22.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:22.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:22.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:27.73	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:35:27.74	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:35:30.33	USH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:35:30.34	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:35:31.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:31.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:31.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:33.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:33.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:33.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:34.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:34.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:34.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:34.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:35.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:35.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:41.69	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:35:43.44	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:35:43.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:43.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:43.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:43.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:38:26.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:26.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:26.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:29.79	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:38:31.53	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:38:32.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:32.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:32.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:41:51.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:42:03.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** 5.2 profile 17
12:42:14.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending to brlow cloud
12:42:44.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud bASE 3700 ft
12:43:51.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:45:31.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft below cloud
12:45:50.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5.3
12:46:39.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:48:03.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:03.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:03.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:13.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:13.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:13.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:14.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:14.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:15.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:15.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:15.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:15.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:15.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:16.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:16.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:18.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:18.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:18.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:18.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:19.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:19.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:20.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:21.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:21.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:21.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:22.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:22.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:48:27.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:48:27.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:48:27.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:55:06.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:55:42.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:55:53.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to FL 230
12:55:59.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 18
13:01:32.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:05:24.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:06:07.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:07.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:07.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:12.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:12.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:12.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:13.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:13.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:14.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:15.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:15.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:15.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:16.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:16.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:17.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:18.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:18.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:18.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:18.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:19.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:20.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:27.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:27.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:27.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:43.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:09:17.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
13:10:14.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:13:34.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:34.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:34.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:36.21	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:13:42.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:42.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:42.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:42.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:43.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:43.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:45.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:45.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:45.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:46.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:46.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:47.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:48.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:48.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:48.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:48.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:49.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:49.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:51.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:51.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:51.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:52.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:53.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:53.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:58.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:58.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:58.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:09.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:15:16.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:16.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:15:16.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:18.10	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:15:19.87	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:15:21.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:21.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:21.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:25.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 23000 ft
13:16:30.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:30.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:30.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:36.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:36.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:37.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:37.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:38.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:38.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:39.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:39.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:39.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:40.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:41.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:41.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:42.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:42.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:42.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:43.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:44.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:44.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:49.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:49.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:49.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:18:59.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:19:17.63	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:19:19.39	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:20:04.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:04.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:04.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:09.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:09.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:09.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:10.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:11.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:11.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:11.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:11.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:11.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:12.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:13.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:13.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:14.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:14.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:14.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:15.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:15.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:16.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:20.99	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:20:22.75	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:20:24.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:20:24.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:20:24.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:21:21.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:22:00.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirrus above and stratocumulus sheet below still
13:25:36.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:26:54.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:54.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:54.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:01.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:01.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:27:01.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:02.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:02.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:03.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:04.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:04.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:04.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:04.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:05.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:05.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:06.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:06.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:06.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:07.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:08.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:08.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:21.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:21.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:21.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:30.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:28:31.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:31.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:31.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:33.11	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:28:34.89	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:28:46.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:46.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:46.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:47.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:47.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:48.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:48.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:48.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:48.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:49.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:50.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:50.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:54.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:54.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:54.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:16.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:16.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:16.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:24.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:24.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:24.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:25.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:25.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:25.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:31.13	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:30:32.89	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:30:33.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:33.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:33.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:26.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:36:20.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:38:17.36	---	-	-	-	-	***
13:38:19.49	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:38:21.24	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:38:33.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirrus above thickening
13:38:43.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:43.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:43.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:49.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:49.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:49.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:50.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:51.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:51.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:38:52.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:52.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:52.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:53.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:53.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:54.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:55.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:55.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:55.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:56.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:56.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:57.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:04.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:04.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:04.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:51.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde
13:40:56.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:40:56.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:40:56.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:00.12	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:41:01.91	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:41:03.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:03.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:03.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:29.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:47:48.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:48:12.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:12.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:12.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:17.04	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:48:18.82	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:48:27.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:27.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:27.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:28.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:28.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:29.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:31.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:31.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:31.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:32.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:33.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:33.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:35.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:35.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:35.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:36.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:36.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:37.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:41.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:41.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:41.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:16.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 4
13:51:10.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:10.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:10.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:13.57	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:51:15.36	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:51:18.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:18.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:18.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:53:52.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:56:02.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:58:22.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:22.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:22.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:24.18	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:58:25.96	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:58:33.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:58:33.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:58:33.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:58:34.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:34.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:35.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:35.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:58:35.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:58:35.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:58:36.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:37.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:37.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:38.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:58:38.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:58:38.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:58:39.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:39.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:40.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:45.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:45.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:45.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:41.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 5
14:01:08.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:09.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:09.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:19.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:19.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:19.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:20.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:20.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:21.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:22.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:22.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:22.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:23.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:23.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:24.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:29.42	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:01:31.20	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:01:31.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:31.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:31.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:36.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:08:33.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:33.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:33.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:36.05	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:08:37.85	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:08:49.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:49.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:49.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:50.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:50.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:50.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:52.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:52.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:52.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:53.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:53.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:54.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:55.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:55.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:55.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:56.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:56.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:57.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:02.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:02.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:02.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:10.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg

14:11:14.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 6
14:12:03.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:03.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:03.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:10.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:10.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:10.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:11.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:11.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:12.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:13.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:13.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:13.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:13.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:14.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:14.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:15.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:15.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:15.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:16.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:16.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:17.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:22.79	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:12:24.56	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:12:25.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:25.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:25.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:46.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:15:03.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:17:30.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** stratocumulus sheet thinning below
14:17:45.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** getting large breaks in cloud
14:19:36.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:36.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:36.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:40.00	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:19:41.78	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:19:51.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:51.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:51.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:52.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:53.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:53.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:57.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:57.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:57.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:57.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:58.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:58.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:00.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:00.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:00.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:00.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:01.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:01.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:06.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:06.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:06.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:17.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:21:21.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 7
14:22:05.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:05.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:05.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:14.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:14.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:14.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:14.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:15.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:15.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:15.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:22:15.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:16.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:16.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:16.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:17.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:18.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:18.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:18.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:19.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:19.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:20.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:25.70	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:22:26.64	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:22:28.39	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:22:30.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:30.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:30.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:12.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:23:47.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:24:15.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** strat sheet almost completely broken up now below
14:25:10.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:25:33.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent (19) into Arica
14:27:47.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** more cloud below
14:27:58.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** solid strat sheet
14:28:15.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** still cirrus above
14:28:29.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:29.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:29.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:29.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:31.31	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:28:33.13	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:28:40.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:40.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:40.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:40.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:41.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:41.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:42.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:42.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:42.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:43.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:44.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:44.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:45.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:45.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:45.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:46.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:46.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:46.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:51.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:51.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:51.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:56.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:31:27.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:38:29.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud breaking up below again
14:41:23.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:41:46.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** passing through a moist layer
14:42:01.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** highidh scattering from neph
14:43:12.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
14:43:24.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** interupted profile
14:43:33.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:44:33.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** clear below cirrus above
14:48:03.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:49:25.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:25.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:26.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:32.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:32.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:49:32.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:33.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:33.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:34.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:36.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:36.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:36.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:37.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:37.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:38.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:39.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:39.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:39.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:40.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:40.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:41.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:48.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:48.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:48.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:00.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:52:34.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:52:35.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:52:57.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning into sun
15:10:23.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:23.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:23.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:28.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:28.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:28.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:29.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:29.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:29.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:31.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:31.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:31.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:32.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:32.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:33.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:35.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:35.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:35.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:36.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:37.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:37.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:42.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:42.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:42.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 4/11/08 Flight No: B 414 Pre-Flighter: KFT.

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☐	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	☒	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	<i>Residue do/son lens</i>
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	☒	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed <u>2/11/08</u> <i>[Signature]</i>
45	☒	ICEX applied		
46	☒	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
47	☒	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B414:

Log	Reason
Instrument Status	may not be correct – Flight Manager asked to check (PAN green on Inst Status but otherwise no evidence of it being operated
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
CCN	The CCN operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	15 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_092941_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_102941_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_112941_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_122941_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_132941_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_142941_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_092926_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_102926_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_112926_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_122926_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_132926_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_142926_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_092920_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_102920_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_112920_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_122920_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_132920_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_142920_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_092933_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_102933_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_112933_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_122933_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_132933_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081104_r0_b414_142933_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.